

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF ASEAN STUDIES

CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA

**INTEGRATING ASEAN PERSPECTIVE IN THE SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION:
AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY OF A TEACHER IN HIGHER EDUCATION**

Thesis Adviser:

JEAN A. SALUDADEZ, Ph. D.
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

07 July 2025

Permission is given for the following people to have access this thesis, subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligation:

Invention (I)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Publication (P)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Confidential (C)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Free (F)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes or <input type="checkbox"/> No

Student's signature:

Thesis adviser signature:

Handwritten signatures in blue ink. The top signature is the student's, and the bottom signature is the thesis adviser's.

INTEGRATING ASEAN PERSPECTIVE IN THE SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION: AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY OF A TEACHER IN HIGHER EDUCATION

“I hereby grant the University of the Philippines a non-exclusive, worldwide, royalty-free license to reproduce, publish and publicly distribute copies of this Academic Work in whatever form subject to the provisions of applicable laws, the provisions of the UP IPR policy and any contractual obligations, as well as more specific permission marking on the Title Page.”

“I specifically allow the University to:

Specifically, I grant the following rights to the University:

- a. Upload a copy of the work in the theses database of the college/school/institute/department and in any other databases available on the public internet*
- b. Publish the work in the college/school/institute/department journal, both in print and electronic or digital format and online; and*
- c. Give open access to the work, thus allowing “fair use” of the work in accordance with the provision of the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), especially for teaching, scholarly and research purposes.*

CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA, July 7, 2025
Signature over Name and Date

Acceptance Page:

This thesis of **CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA** titled: **“INTEGRATING ASEAN PERSPECTIVE IN THE SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION: AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY OF A TEACHER IN HIGHER EDUCATION”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of ASEAN Studies.

JEAN A. SALUDADEZ, Ph. D.
Chair, Advisory Committee

09/29/2025
(Date)

EMELY D. DICOLEN, Ph. D.
Member, Advisory Committee

09/29/2025
(Date)

PRIMO G. GARCIA, Ph. D.
Member, Advisory Committee

09/30/2025
(Date)

FINAFIOR TAYLAN, DProfSt, RSW

Dean

Faculty of Management and Development Studies

10/01/2025

(Date)

Bibliographical Sketch

Christian Jessie B. Bala is the fourth among five children of Wilfredo S. Bala and Maria Magdalena C. Bertos. He currently works as a higher education teacher at Calabanga Community College in Calabanga, Camarines Sur, where he contributes to the academic growth of his students. He resides in Zone 4, San Juan-San Lorenzo, Minalabac, Camarines Sur.

In 2022, Christian earned a Graduate Certificate in ASEAN Studies (GCAS) from the University of the Philippines Open University and is currently pursuing a Master of ASEAN Studies at the same institution, where he honed his knowledge in regional development.

Beyond his academic endeavors, Christian is committed to community service as a member of the Rotary Club of Goa Partido, a non-profit organization located in Goa, Camarines Sur. His professional and extracurricular activities demonstrate his dedication to education and community development in the region.

Acknowledgment

The completion of this thesis would not have been possible without the unwavering support, guidance, and encouragement of those who stood by me throughout this journey.

To my almighty God, whose wisdom, grace and blessings to overcome the challenges along the way.

To my thesis adviser, Dr. Jean A. Saludadez for providing insightful feedback and unwavering encouragement through this journey. Your expertise and patience have been instrumental in shaping and guiding this work.

To my professors and mentors at the University of the Philippines Open University, whose wisdom and dedication have profoundly influenced my academic work.

To my beloved family and to my love, your boundless love, patience and unwavering faith in me have been my greatest source of strength.

To my friends and colleagues, your unwavering support during late nights and challenging moments has made this process more manageable and meaningful.

To my love, your presence has been a constant source of inspiration and comfort. Thank you for believing in me, for cheering me on, and for standing beside me through every step of this process.

Finally, to everyone who contributed in any way to the completion of this thesis. Your generosity and guidance have been invaluable, and I am forever grateful.

Dedication

To my family, whose unwavering support and love have been my anchor throughout this journey.

To my beloved father, who left this world while I was in pursuit of my dreams at UPOU. Your strength, wisdom, and quiet encouragement continue to guide me each day. This work is as much yours as it is mine.

To my friends, thank you for the laughter, understanding, and companionship that helped me through the challenges.

And to my love—in all its forms, for giving me the courage to continue, the patience to endure, and the joy that made every step worthwhile.

Abstract

The study answers the following questions: (1) “What are the higher education teachers’ practices in incorporating ASEAN in teaching Social Studies?” and (2) “What are the perspectives that underlies the higher education teacher’s practices for integrating ASEAN in teaching Social Studies?”

The researcher utilized autoethnography and autoethnomethodology as both research frameworks and research methods. As research framework, Autoethnography examines teaching experiences and perspectives for incorporating ASEAN in higher education, while autoethnomethodology identifies teaching practices for integrating ASEAN in teaching BSED Social Studies. As research method, it employs reflective narratives, critical self-inquiry and curriculum analysis. The data sources include course syllabus, course lectures, and course assessments.

The results showed that there are six (6) practices in incorporating ASEAN in teaching Social Studies and three (3) perspectives in incorporating ASEAN in teaching social studies. The results impact ASEANOLGY in higher education. First, the inclusion of ASEAN in the course syllabus as culminating activity, as a subtopic in the broader topic of “Asian Regionalism” and as a central topic in the course syllabus in Asian Studies helps students learn that the Philippines is an integral part of ASEAN and help build their identity as ASEAN citizens. Second, Filipino educators have the responsibility to teach students the role of ASEAN in strengthening regional cooperation through learning the difference between regionalism from globalization. Last, promoting respect for diversity and cultural competence within ASEAN community through experiential learning such as culminating activity emphasizes the role of ASEAN not only as a political and economic organization but also as a

framework for regional identity. The result offers recommendations to meet Philippine educational standards.

Keywords: Culturally Responsive Teaching (CRT); Curriculum Integration; Higher Education; Regional Cooperation and Integration; ASEAN Identity; Future Educators, Teacher Training, Institutional Support

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
University Permission Page	ii
Acceptance Page	iii
Biographical Sketch	iv
Acknowledgment	v
Dedication	vi
Table of Contents	ix
List of Tables	xi
List of Figures	xx
ABSTRACT	vii
CHAPTER 1: RATIONALE	1
Integration of ASEAN in the Higher Education Curriculum	1
Integration of ASEAN in Social Studies in Higher Education	2
CHAPTER 2: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	4
ASEAN Integration in Higher Education Institutions	4
Culturally Responsive Teaching	7
Integration of 21 st century skills	8
CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH FRAMEWORK	10
Autoethnography/Ethnomethodology as Theoretical Framework	10
Research Questions	12
CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	13
Data gathering procedure	13
Data source	14

Data analysis	16
CHAPTER 5: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	22
HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHER’S PRACTICES IN INCORPORATING ASEAN IN TEACHING SOCIAL STUDIES	22
Including selected topics about ASEAN in teaching a course titled “Asian Studies”,	22
Incorporating ASEAN in teaching “Asian Regionalism”	27
Teaching the nature and concept of ASEAN including principles of ASEAN as the last topic in the course syllabus	31
Teaching students to research and present their assigned topics on ASEAN with course guidelines and rubrics	44
Teaching the contribution and significance of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies”	47
Requiring the students to showcase the nation and cultural identity of ASEAN member countries and its neighboring countries through creative methods	61
HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHER’S PERSPECTIVE IN INTEGRATING ASEAN IN SOCIAL STUDIES	66
ASEAN has to be appreciated by the students that may help building ASEAN identity	66
Students as future educators should have a deep appreciation of the commitment and effort of ASEAN to achieve regional cooperation among its member countries	69
Respect for diversity and cultural competence to develop regional citizenship	70
Relationship between teaching practices and perspectives	71
CHAPTER 6: SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	74
Summary	73

Contribution to ASEANOLOGY	76
Recommendations	77
REFERENCES	xv
APPENDICES	
LIST OF TABLES	
Table 1. Data Set	17
LIST OF FIGURES	
Figure 1. Course Syllabus from school year 2022-2023	22
Figure 2. Course Syllabus from school year 2023-2024	23
Figure 3. Course syllabus from school year 2024-2025	23
Figure 4. Introducing ASEAN as a subtopic in Asian Regionalism	27
Figure 5. Introducing ASEAN to BSED Social Studies students	32
Figure 6. My discussion of ASEAN	33
Figure 7. Research activity with assigned topics on ASEAN with course guidelines and rubrics (page 1)	44
Figure 8. Research activity with assigned topics on ASEAN with course guidelines and rubrics (page 2)	45
Figure 9. Research activity with assigned topics on ASEAN with course guidelines and rubrics (page 3)	46
Figure 10. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 1)	48
Figure 11. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 2)	49
Figure 12. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 3)	50

Figure 3. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 4)	51
Figure 14. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 5)	52
Figure 15. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 6)	53
Figure 16. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 7)	54
Figure 17. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 8)	55
Figure 18. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 9)	56
Figure 19. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 10)	57
Figure 20. My guidelines on culminating activity	62

CHAPTER I

RATIONALE

This chapter presents the purpose of presenting the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) in higher education based on the practices and perspective of a higher education teacher equipped with the 21st century skills that are essential to promote regional awareness and develop a sense of identity within the ASEAN community. It also recognizes underprivileged higher education institutions, such as Calabanga Community College, where institutional support promotes transformative education.

Integration of ASEAN in Higher Education

The Philippines have low students' perception about ASEAN. It may be taught briefly and theoretically in higher education institutions. ASEAN is treated as a subtopic in general education subjects. It may often discuss its institutional structure, but it has limited discussions about it in improving social mobility, such as education and providing jobs. Higher education institutions have lack of local research about ASEAN, making it difficult to contextualize it for students. ASEAN awareness may not reach higher education institutions in rural areas and not prominently featured in extracurricular activities and events.

Integrating ASEAN into higher education helps students understand the region's history, cultures, economies, and political systems and promote ASEAN through research and curricular and extracurricular activities and events. It aligns to

the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC), where it helps students to learn cross-cultural understanding and adaptability in diverse work environments to become ASEAN citizens.

Integration of ASEAN in Social Studies Education

The curriculum in the Philippines dominated by Philippines history and citizenship, and ASEAN may seem less important. ASEAN is often included as a political and economic organization in Southeast Asia. It has no deep exploration of its history, economy, and political dynamics. Students don't see the relevance of ASEAN in addressing real-life issues because it is oversimplified rather than celebrated. Many teachers often fail to localize ASEAN because they have limited training, and teaching materials and tools are outdated.

Integrating ASEAN into teaching BSED social studies is critical for developing regional identity. Its meaningful framework exposes regional dynamics, cultural heritage, and global citizenship. As future educators, they must understand ASEAN principles and consider how to teach them to the next generation.

It shows how student-centered approaches such as culturally responsive teaching and contextualized content, interactive activities, and reflective assessments improve regional awareness and develop 21st century skills, such as critical thinking, collaboration, communication and creativity.

The study aims to identify the higher education teacher's practices in integrating ASEAN in teaching BSED Social Studies. It also explores the underlying perspectives

that inform these practices. It examines the relationship between teaching practices and these underlying perspectives that may contribute to ASEANOLOGY. It focuses on the experience of a teacher in Calabanga Community College, a local higher education institution located in Calabanga, Camarines Sur. The teacher will serve a dual role as subject and researcher. As a subject, he teaches a course titled “Asian Studies” in the BSED Social Studies program. As a researcher, the teacher is pursuing Master of ASEAN Studies in University of the Philippines – Open University. However, it is limited only to the Calabanga Community College and does not extend to other higher education institutions. The findings can provide insights to support other higher education institutions to promote ASEAN awareness.

The study shows significance for stakeholders. First, it emphasizes the role of the researcher for innovating education by capturing firsthand experience for doing this initiative. Second, it provides recommendations for policymakers for refining the curriculum that promotes inclusivity. Third, it empowers local higher education institutions to enhance their academic programs by contextualizing teaching content based on the historical, cultural and social backgrounds of students, while meeting global education standards. Fourth, it provides recommendations for higher education teachers to adapt the results into their teaching practices. Last, it helps students to bridge theoretical knowledge with real-life applications through interactive activities and reflective assessments.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter explores the connection between ASEAN integration, utilization of culturally responsive teaching, and the integration of 21st century skills to identify and address the gaps in integrating ASEAN in underprivileged higher education institutions such as Calabanga Community College.

ASEAN Integration in Higher Education Institutions

The joint statement of the Brunei-Darussalam, Indonesia, Malaysia, and Philippines during the 9th East Asia Growth Area (BIMP-EAGA) Summit acknowledged the role of youth in promoting ASEAN centrality through sustainable development. It supports ASEAN Youth Volunteer Program (AYVP) and strengthen sense of identity and belonging through voluntary community service in rural development, disaster risk management, health, education, and environmental protection, inclusivity for disabled groups, and entrepreneurial opportunities. The summit encouraged ASEAN to use 2012 ASEAN Curriculum Sourcebook to strengthen ASEAN across various education systems. Member states were encouraged to translate into local languages and incorporate ASEAN into their curriculum. The summit also reaffirmed a strong commitment to enhance human resource development across the region. It boosts productivity and prosperity through collaborative projects, such as the ASEAN Credit Transfer System (ACTS) and TVET Quality Assurance Framework.

During his speech at the 13th ASEAN summit, Prime Minister Lee Hsein Loong emphasized the lack of foundation of ASEAN in its population. He stressed the need to improve their skills and talent within the ASEAN community to maintain its competitiveness, maximize the benefits of globalization and promote regional cooperation among ASEAN member states.

Prime Minister Lee also emphasized the importance of celebrating ASEAN in higher education institutions. In Singapore led commemorative activities in the 40th anniversary of ASEAN in 2007. Thailand proposed the integration of ASEAN in the higher education curriculum and implementing the annual celebration of ASEAN friendship day every August 8.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DEPED) committed to promote digital education reforms within ASEAN and advocates for policies and initiatives that empower students to prepare future challenges. The ASEAN digital masterplan 2025 aims to make the region a leading digital community through digital literacy. Member states should create roadmaps that integrate technology into education to promote digital skills. The ASEAN Declaration on the Digital Transformation of Education Systems addresses issues such as digital divide and learning.

The Philippines also been proactive in implementing reforms in digital learning, such as DepEd Digital Education 2028, The digital integration of higher education proposed by CHED, and the digital skills training by Technical Education Skills Development Authority (TESDA). It helps students to learn the integration of digital skills in their workplace.

Heryadi et. al. (2019) ASEAN University Network (AUN) supports neo-functional theories emerged in the historical legacies, such as colonialism and the

Cold War to improve economic and political integration. However, even if AUN supports regional integration in higher education, only larger higher education institutions can benefit due to their administrative competence, financial stability, and infrastructure. On the other hand, smaller higher education institutions were experiencing lack of ASEAN centrality as they were underrepresented in the AUN. Its local adaptation remains unclear. The gap requires comprehensive analysis of the adaptability of AUN in the smaller higher education institution. My research aims to understand how Calabanga Community College participates in regional cooperation despite limited resources. It offers practical recommendations for capacity building and policy making.

Katigbak and Amante (2019) found that higher education institutions in Laguna and Quezon were dedicated to advocating all three pillars through curriculum development to promote academic and research mobility. However, there is a gap in promoting ASEAN awareness, as it varies in resources and institutional support and readiness. There is a lack of financial resources and insufficient government support. The gaps suggest that teachers and students should expand the exchange of teaching practices to gain new insights. Public and private sectors should collaborate to recognize the effectiveness of ASEAN integration into higher education institutions.

Pasciana and Iriany (2018) argue that ASEAN integration in secondary and tertiary education plays a crucial role in boosting women's involvement in the workforce. However, women still face income inequality and limited resources in employment because of unequal access to education and gender discrimination. My research examines the role of higher education to centralize ASEAN awareness on gender equality and equal access to education.

Daungkaew and Chongcharoen (2016) noted the role of higher education in centralizing ASEAN Economic Community. The Office of the Higher Education Commission (OHEC) has created the Thai Qualifications Framework and 11th Higher Education Development Plan to strengthen education and promote multilingualism and workforce readiness. However, Thailand struggles with poor English proficiency among teachers and students, lack of technical and vocational skills need for employment, and lack of trainings on quality assurance system. My research provides recommendations for curriculum developers and policy makers to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions.

Culturally Responsive Teaching

Karatas (2020) argues that Culturally Responsive Teaching (CRT) requires empathy and respect for diverse cultures. CRT uses native language to contextualize content to develop reflexivity. It helps students to explore cultural diversity and develop cultural sensitivity.

However, there is a gap in utilizing CRT for pre-service teachers. They lack training in utilizing CRT in the classroom. My research examines the utilization of CRT in teaching BSED Social Studies students to prepare them as future educators advocating for shared regional identity in the classroom.

Cawaling-Mauntol and Padua (2022) stated the Culturally Responsive Teaching uses students' backgrounds to promote inclusivity. They identified four strategies in teaching CRT. First, educators should use collaborative learning strategies such as group work to develop socialization. Second, educators should encourage students to utilize ICT tools in presentations and engage with art-of-

questioning to develop confidence and reflect on their positionality to learn self-expression. Third, educators should adapt to the local resources to meet students' needs, and last, educators should help students to express their ideas into native language before translating it to English.

Cawaling-Mauntol and Padua found three themes that emerged from teachers' perspectives on how to use personalized learning in Culturally Responsive Teaching. First, personalized learning localizes content from standard resources to develop language skills and helps students to foster unity despite their various backgrounds. Second, personalized learning prevents students from fragmenting their learning. Last, personalized learning interactive activities such as group presentations to enhance students' engagement.

However, higher education institutions failed to value regional integration cultural sensitivity in the curriculum. Also, cultural conflicts among students, lack of teachers' collaboration and lack of training hinder the implementation of culturally responsive teaching in the classroom.

My research addresses these gaps by utilizing ASEAN as an example to teach cultural sensitivity among students and analyze its impact through autoethnography and autoethnomethodology to provide practical recommendations for future studies.

Integration of 21st Century Skills

Birru (2024) found that teachers play a role in nurturing 21st century skills, such as communication, collaboration, creativity and critical thinking, through utilization of information and communication technology, innovation skills, and life skills in the curriculum. He recommends that curriculum developers and policy makers should

create programs to teach 21st century skills in the classroom. Pre-service teachers are encouraged to include interactive activities in their lesson plans to enhance 21st century skills.

However, the outdated curriculums, lack of teaching resources and lack of training hinder the integration of 21st century skills. Through autoethnography and autoethnomethodology, my research utilizes ASEAN to integrate 21st century skills. It offers recommendations for curriculum developers and policy makers to prepare pre-service teachers as future educators.

Garba et. al. (2015) found that ICT tools help improve the teaching and learning process. Computers, projectors, and internet helps educators to develop interactive learning.

However, many teachers lack Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) and it affects how teachers use ICT Tools in teaching. Teachers often view ICT tools in retrieving information and creating presentations. But they lack knowledge and skills for using ICT to assess and evaluate students' learning. My research examines the integration of ICT tools in teaching ASEAN in BSED Social studies. It includes the benefits and challenges that I experience in utilizing ICT in my teaching practices.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

This chapter presents autoethnography and autoethnomethodology as theoretical framework. It involves personal experiences, perspectives, and practices to develop insights for promoting regional identity.

Autoethnography/Autoethnomethodology as Theoretical Framework

My research frameworks are autoethnography and autoethnomethodology. Autoethnography allows myself to examine my teaching experiences and perspectives for ASEAN integration in higher education, while autoethnomethodology allows myself to examine teaching practices for ASEAN integration in teaching BSED Social Studies.

Ellis, Adam, and Brochner (2011) describe autoethnography as a qualitative approach that blends autobiography and ethnography. It involves using personal experiences (“auton”) to interpret and analyze cultural contexts (“ethno”) through narrative writing (“graphy”). Narratives should support empirical data, such as field notes, personal journals, and record documents

Autoethnography demands empirical rigor such as reflexivity, cultural sensitivity and contextualization. It is not evaluated by scientific metrics but by resonance, credibility, reflexivity, and ethical responsibility.

While critics argue that autoethnography lacks objectivity and generalizability, autoethnographers contend that it provides meaningful insights and connections to experiential knowledge.

Wall (2006) defends autoethnography connects personal experiences with broader systematic issues to reveal institutional biases such as marginalized and local populations.

On the other hand, autoethnomethodology is a qualitative approach that examines the peoples' everyday unspoken practices to maintain social order in daily life. Autoethnomethodology has three elements, namely Reflexivity, Accountability, and Indexicality. Reflexivity describes how social context influences people's perceptions. Accountability describes performing actions that others understand and justify. Indexicality describes that expressions and behaviors cannot be fully understood in isolation.

Garfinkel (as cited in Meier zu Verl and Meyer, 2022) uses the "documentary method of interpretation" such as the sequence of timing of actions and the significance of artifacts in collaborative process. It emphasizes how detailed, systematic analysis of real-life experiences helps people to create social order. Professionally, it emphasizes analyzing daily interactions rather than theoretical analysis.

Research Questions

The framework specifically answers the research hquestions:

1. What are a higher education teacher's practices in incorporating ASEAN in teaching Social Studies?
2. What are the perspective that underlie the higher education teacher's practices in integrating ASEAN in teaching Social Studies?

CHAPTER IV

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents autoethnography and autoethnomethodology as qualitative approach. It also includes data gathering procedures, data sources, data analysis and data set.

I will utilize autoethnography and autoethnomethodology as qualitative approach. Autoethnography explores my experiences and perspectives in incorporating ASEAN in curriculum in higher education, while autoethnomethodology explores my practices in teaching ASEAN in BSED Social Studies program.

I assume the dual roles of both a participant and observer, which examine my teaching experiences, perspectives, and practices. I view personal vulnerability, emotional engagement, and exploring identity as a valuable source of insight, which aligns with the criteria of resonance and credibility as mentioned by Ellis, Adam, and Brochner (2011).

Data Gathering Procedure

My study examines ASEAN integration in the course “Asian Studies” in the BSED Social Studies program at Calabanga Community College. It can be done through reflective narratives, critical self-inquiry, and curriculum analysis.

First, reflective practices narratives will function as the principal method of data collection. I will use my reflective narratives based on my experiences for integrating ASEAN.

Second, critical self-inquiry will be conducted alongside my reflective narratives to examine my teaching practices within broader institutional, cultural, and political contexts.

Last, curriculum analysis will examine how ASEAN is included in the course syllabus, course lectures, and course assessments and how it supports the ASEAN's goal of fostering regional identity among BSED Social Studies students.

Data Sources

Course syllabus

The course syllabus includes selected topics about on the course titled "Asian Studies", focusing on the interconnection of ASEAN countries in terms of culture, history, and trade; explain the regional dynamics of Asia within economic, political and cultural contexts; and understand the nature and concept of ASEAN.

This practice underlies the perspective that ASEAN has to be appreciated by the students that may help build ASEAN identity.

Course lectures

There are two lectures that are included in the data set. The first course lecture incorporates ASEAN in teaching the topic "Asian Regionalism", which the final topic in the course "Asian Studies", and covers the difference between globalization and regionalization, along with benefits and challenges.

The second course lecture is teaching the nature and concept of ASEAN, including principles of ASEAN as the last topic in the course syllabus by connecting their previous knowledge they learned about the history of Asia as a precursor in the foundation of ASEAN. Students can learn about ASEAN's principles, such as non-interference, consensus-decision making, and respect for sovereignty, and see how ASEAN promotes regional cooperation and integration while effectively tackling issues through its mechanisms and processes. Students can also understand the significance of ASEAN in addressing and comprehending broader global and regional issues.

These practices underlie the perspective that BSED Social Studies students as future educators should have a deep appreciation and commitment and effort of ASEAN to achieve regional cooperation among its member countries.

Course Assessments

There are three course assessments included in the data set. The first course assessment is the reflection activity as a final examination in the course "Asian Studies" which enables students to learn about the role and importance of ASEAN in the "Asian Studies" course by utilizing the course guidelines and rubrics. They will interact with ASEAN personally, presenting their analysis to meet academic standards, evaluating their comprehension of ASEAN as a concept, and applying these concepts to Asian Regionalism to practical situations.

The second course assessment is asynchronous activity which enables students to create a presentation of their assigned topics related to ASEAN. The objective is to teach students how to research and present their topics in accordance with the course guidelines and rubrics.

These course assessments underlie the perspective that BSED Social Studies students as future educators should have a deep appreciation for the commitment and effort of ASEAN to achieve regional cooperation among its member countries.

The third course assessment is the culminating activity which enable students to teach the contribution and significance of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics by engaging with ASEAN on a personal level to present their analysis and meet academic standards, assess their understanding the concept of ASEAN, and apply the theoretical concepts of Asian Regionalism on real-life scenarios.

This practice underlie the perspective that respect for diversity and cultural competence to develop regional citizenship.

Data Analysis

These naturally occurring data found were categorized into three, the course syllabus, course lectures, and course assessments.

Table 1*Data set*

Naturally occurring data	Practices	Perspectives
Course Syllabus	Included selected topics about on the course titled “Asian Studies”, focusing on the interconnection of ASEAN countries in terms of culture, history, and trade; explain the regional dynamics of Asia within economic, political and cultural contexts; and understand the nature and concept of ASEAN.	ASEAN has to be appreciated by the students that may help build ASEAN identity
Course Syllabus	Incorporating ASEAN in teaching the topic “Asian Regionalism”, which the final topic in the course “Asian Studies”, and covers the difference between globalization and	BSED Social Studies as future educators should have a deep appreciation and commitment and effort of ASEAN to achieve regional cooperation

	regionalization, along with benefits and challenges.	among its member countries.
Powerpoint presentation	Teaching the nature and concept of ASEAN, including principles of ASEAN as the last topic in the course syllabus by connecting their previous knowledge they learned about the history of Asia as a precursor in the foundation of ASEAN. Students can learn about ASEAN's principles, such as non-interference, consensus-decision making, and respect for sovereignty, and see how ASEAN promotes regional cooperation and integration while effectively tackling issues through its mechanisms and processes. Students can also understand the	BSED Social Studies students as future educators should have a deep appreciation and commitment and effort of ASEAN to achieve regional cooperation among its member countries.

significance of ASEAN in
addressing and
comprehending broader
global and regional issues

Course Assessments

Asynchronous activity: Teaching students to BSED Social Studies
Students should create on research and present their students as future
their assigned topic about assigned topics on educators should have a
ASEAN ASEAN with course deep appreciation and
guidelines and rubrics. commitment and effort of
ASEAN to achieve
regional cooperation
among its member
countries.

Culminating activity as Requiring the students to Respect for diversity and
final examination in the showcase the nation and cultural competence to
course "Asian Studies" cultural identity of ASEAN develop regional
with corresponding member countries and its citizenship
guidelines and rubrics neighboring countries
through creative methods
and integrating different
disciplines through
similarities of culture in

food, attire, government
system, and flag

Reflection activity as final examination in Asian Studies

Teaching the contribution and significance of ASEAN in the course titled “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics by engaging on ASEAN personally, presenting their analysis to meet academic standards, evaluating their comprehension of ASEAN as a concept, and applying these concepts to Asian Regionalism to real-life scenarios

BSED Social Studies students as future educators should have a deep appreciation and commitment and effort of ASEAN to achieve regional cooperation among its member countries.

/

The thesis committee conducted member checking to the researcher to ensure credibility and trustworthiness. They also tracked insights from the initial planning to the final reflections to the researcher to maintain transparency.

Although it focuses primarily on my teaching experiences, perspectives, and practices, clearance from the Faculty of Management and Development Studies Research and Ethics Committee was obtained to ensure my research adheres to the ethical standards of the university.

CHAPTER V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents six teaching practices that I used in incorporating ASEAN in teaching BSED Social studies and the three perspectives that underlie my teaching practices. It also discusses the relationship between the teaching practices and teaching perspectives.

Higher Education Teacher's Practices In Incorporating ASEAN in Teaching Social Studies

Including selected topics in teaching a course titled "Asian Studies" specifically how the interconnection of ASEAN countries in terms of culture, history, and trade; explain the regional dynamics of Southeast Asia within economic, political, and cultural contexts; and understand the concept and nature of ASEAN.

Figure 1. Course Syllabus from school year 2022-2023

FINAL EXAMINATION – Students will conduct "Asian Nations' Parade, a culminating activity which emphasizes the cultural identity of Asia, particularly in Southeast Asia.	2 hours
V. TEXTBOOKS AND REFERENCES	
1. Coffin, J. (2002). <i>Western civilization, their history and their culture</i> . New York: W.W. Norton & Co., Inc.	
2. Coronado, M., Foe J., Pierco, C. (2001). <i>Making sense of world history</i> . Makati City: The Bookmark, Inc.	
3. Irapta A.C. and Duka, C.D. (2005). <i>Introduction to Asia: History, culture and civilization</i> . Manila: Rex Book store	
4. DK. 2018. <i>Timelines of History: The Ultimate Visual Guide to the Events That Shaped the World</i> , 2nd Edition	
5. Leano R. & Bautista, A. (2011). <i>Asian civilizations</i> . Manila: Mindshapers Co., Inc.	
6. Murphey, R. (2000). <i>A history of Asia</i> . Singapore: Pearson Education Asia Pte Ltd.	
7. National Geographic. 2018. <i>National Geographic Almanac 2019: Hot New Science – Incredible Photographs - Maps, Facts, Info graphics & More Paperback</i> .	
VI. COURSE REQUIREMENTS	
1. Student must obtain a minimum final rating of at least 75% or equivalent to 3.0 to pass the subject.	
2. Student must pass at least two major examinations, midterm and final.	
3. Students must comply with the requirements on or before the scheduled date.	
4. A student who committed more than 20% of total recitation day will merit 5.0.	
VII. COURSE EVALUATION	
1. The final grade will be computed based on the following criteria:	
Written Works	25%
Examinations	25%
Summative	15%
Performance	35%
	100%
2. The weight for each grading period are as follows: Midterm 40%, and Final 60%.	
3. For delayed examination, refer to the provisions in the Student Handbook.	
VIII. CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT	
Students of this course are expected to:	
OBE SYLLABUS IN CORSE 12 - ASIAN STUDIES	
Page 9	

Figure 2. Course Syllabus from school year 2023-2024

At the end of these weeks, the preservice teacher (PST) should be able to:	K. Asian Regionalism a. Difference between Globalization and Regionalism b. Regional Integration c. Challenges to Regionalism d. NATO e. ASEAN	Lecture-Discussion	1.PowerPoint presentation 2.Hand outs 3.Worksheets 4. Video Presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recitation Short Quiz 	6 hours	
FINAL EXAMINTION – 1 hour					2 hours	

V. TEXTBOOKS AND REFERENCES

- Coffin, J. (2002). Western civilization, their history and their culture. New York: W.W. Norton & Co., Inc.
- Coronado, M., Foe J., Parco, C. (2001). Making sense of world history. Makati City: The Bookmark, Inc.
- Irapta A.C. and Duka, C.D. (2005). Introduction to Asia: History, culture and civilization. Manila: Rex Book store
- DK. 2018. Timelines of History: The Ultimate Visual Guide to the Events That Shaped the World, 2nd Edition
- Leano R. & Bautista, A. (2011). Asian civilizations. Manila: Mindshapers Co., Inc.
- Murphey, R. (2000). A history of Asia. Singapore: Pearson Education Asia Pte Ltd.
- National Geographic. 2018. National Geographic Almanac 2019: Hot New Science - Incredible Photographs - Maps, Facts, Info graphics & More Paperback.

VI. COURSE REQUIREMENTS

- Student must obtain a minimum final rating of at least 75% or equivalent to 3.0 to pass the subject.
- Student must pass at least two major examinations, midterm and final.
- Students must comply with the requirements on or before the scheduled date.
- A student who committed more than 20% of total recitation day will merit 5.0.

VII. COURSE EVALUATION

- The final grade will be computed based on the following criteria:
Written Works - 25%
Examinations 25%

OBE SYLLABUS IN MCSSE 12 - ASIAN STUDIES
Page 9

Figure 3. Course syllabus from school year 2024-2025

At the end of these weeks, the preservice teacher (PST) should be able to:	K. Asian Regionalism a. Difference between Globalization and Regionalism b. Regional Integration c. Challenges to Regionalism d. NATO e. ASEAN	Lecture-Discussion	1.PowerPoint presentation 2.Hand outs 3.Worksheets 4. Video Presentations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recitation Short Quiz 	3 hours	
At the end of these weeks, the preservice teacher (PST) should be able to:	L. ASEAN a. The nature of ASEAN b. ASEAN Institutional Structure c. ASEAN Extenral Relations d. Key Achievements of ASEAN e. ASEAN challenges f. ASEAN look forward 2025	Lecture-Discussion	1.PowerPoint presentation 2.Hand outs 3.Worksheets 4. Group activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recitation Reflection Activities 	6 hours	
FINAL EXAMINTION – 1 hour					2 hours	

V. TEXTBOOKS AND REFERENCES

- Coffin, J. (2002). Western civilization, their history and their culture. New York: W.W. Norton & Co., Inc.
- Coronado, M., Foe J., Parco, C. (2001). Making sense of world history. Makati City: The Bookmark, Inc.
- Irapta A.C. and Duka, C.D. (2005). Introduction to Asia: History, culture and civilization. Manila: Rex Book store
- DK. 2018. Timelines of History: The Ultimate Visual Guide to the Events That Shaped the World, 2nd Edition
- Leano R. & Bautista, A. (2011). Asian civilizations. Manila: Mindshapers Co., Inc.
- Murphey, R. (2000). A history of Asia. Singapore: Pearson Education Asia Pte Ltd.
- National Geographic. 2018. National Geographic Almanac 2019: Hot New Science - Incredible Photographs - Maps, Facts, Info graphics & More Paperback.

OBE SYLLABUS IN MCSSE 12 - ASIAN STUDIES
Page 9

Throughout my teaching experience, I have revised my course syllabus annually to improve content and student engagement. In my first year, I incorporated ASEAN into the culminating activity to highlight the connection between cultural elements and cuisines of Southeast Asia and its neighboring countries. Students were given guidelines and rubrics, which include three criteria, such as content quality (50 points), creativity (30 points) and food connection (20 points).

In my second year, I included ASEAN as a subtopic in the broader topic titled “Asian Regionalism”. I differentiate globalization and regionalism, explain the reasons of Asian countries in forming regional organization, add factors leading to regional cooperation, and identify the challenges to regionalism. Then I used ASEAN as an example of regional organization in Asia.

In my third year, I revised the course syllabus again and introduced ASEAN as a central topic. I include 7 subtopics, which include the nature of ASEAN, institutional structure of ASEAN, ASEAN External Relations, key achievements and challenges of ASEAN, and ASEAN future outlook. I utilized interactive activities to discuss ASEAN. It includes asynchronous activity with guidelines and rubrics, which allow students to research and present their assigned topic. In assessing their output through rubric, I include six criteria, which includes content accuracy and depth, organization and structure, visual aids, delivery such as clarity, pace and confidence, engagement and instruction, time management and creativity and originality. In evaluating their outputs, I used Likert scale which includes Excellent (4), good (3), Satisfactory (2) and Needs Improvement (1).

I also provided a reflective assessment with guidelines and rubrics. It was based on Milner's (2007) framework to assess their historical, cultural and social backgrounds as Filipinos and connect in their identity as ASEAN citizens. In assessing their outputs through rubric, I include seven criteria, which include content and ideas, organization, critical thinking, relevance and reflection, language, use of examples, creativity and engagement. In evaluating their outputs, I used likert scale, which includes 4 (excellent), 3 (proficient), 2 (satisfactory), and 1 (needs improvement). In scoring guide, I categorized the score into Excellent (A, 28-24), Proficient (B, 23-20), Satisfactory (C, 16-19), and Needs Improvement (D/F, 15 and below).

The revisions I made in the course syllabus were based on my experiences. When I incorporated ASEAN in the culminating activity, it made me realize that it helps students to build regional awareness. I utilized teacher-centered approach to include ASEAN as a subtopic in the broader topic of "Asian Regionalism" in the course Asian Studies. However, I observed that the discussion was compressed, and lack of students' engagement.

When I centralized ASEAN as a topic, I utilized culturally responsive teaching as student-centered approach. I also include interactive activities and reflective assessments. Milner's (2007) framework helps the students to reflect on their positionality as Filipino and connect to their identity as ASEAN citizens.

The findings indicate a successful integration of ASEAN as a central topic within the course syllabus. Initially, I used the teacher-centered approach. However, transitions to a student-centered approach using culturally responsive teaching, interactive activities and reflective assessment. Heryadi et. al. (2019), Garba et. al. (2015), and Katigbak and Amante (2019), supports this shift, stressing the need for

inclusive teaching along with curriculum alignment. Further, tools such as Milner's (2007) framework proved effective in promoting ASEAN identity and student engagement through culturally responsive teaching and develop 21st century skills.

However, Heryadi et. al. (2019) contend that ASEAN integration in underprivileged higher education institutions is deficient and lacks initiatives to promote ASEAN. It supports my initiative to revise the course syllabus every school year. I integrate ASEAN as a culminating activity in my first year of teaching, I include as a subtopic in the broader subtopic of "Asian Regionalism" in the course Asian Studies in my second year of teaching, and I centralized ASEAN as a topic in the course Asian Studies in my third year of teaching. Katigbak and Amante (2019) added that ASEAN is a complex topic, and it should be centralized in the general education courses in the higher education institutions.

Karatas (2020) and Cawaling-Mauntol-Padua (2002) emphasized that contextualizing concepts based on students' backgrounds promotes inclusivity. Teachers should act as curriculum developers by continuously refining their teaching approaches to integrate with 21st century skills. Garba et. al. (2015) found that the transition from teacher-centered to student centered approach helps students promote student engagement. Heryadi et. al. (2019) added that student-centered approach helps students to reflect on their personal identities.

Pasciana and Iriany (2018) found that Milner's (2007) framework enhances cultural sensitivity and awareness. It supports my initiative to utilize Milner's (2007) framework to help students to reflect on their positionalities as Filipino and connect to their identities as ASEAN citizens. Garba et. al. (2015) supports my initiative to include

ICT Tools in interactive activities and reflective assessments to develop 21st century skills.

Utilizing ASEAN as a concrete example to contrast globalization and regionalism has proven to be essential. Pasciana and Iriany (2018) supports the role of ASEAN to exemplify regional cooperation.

Incorporating ASEAN in the topic “Asian Regionalism” as the last topic in the course “Asian Studies” which includes the difference between globalization and regionalism, and its benefits and challenges.

Figure 4. Introducing ASEAN as a subtopic in Asian Regionalism

I included ASEAN as a subtopic in the broader topic of “Asian Regionalism”. The objectives include explain the difference between globalization and regionalism,

identify the factors that promote integration in Asia, and how Asian countries address the challenges posed both by globalization and regionalism. I began by clarifying the distinction between “globalization” and “regionalism” regionalism in terms of nature, market, society and culture, humanitarian aid and technological advances. Then, I explained the reasons of Asian countries to form regional organization, such as the need for military defenses, economic crises, conservation of natural resources and protection for independence. I added factors leading to regional cooperation, such as free trade and similar cultures, goals, and security needs. I also identified the challenges to regionalism, which includes resurgence of militant nationalism and populism, continuing financial crisis, and differing visions of regionalism.

I discussed ASEAN as an example of regional cooperation. I included its member countries, which includes Indonesia, Thailand, Malaysia, Singapore, Philippines, Cambodia, Brunei-Darussalam, Myanmar and Laos. I also presented each country’s capital, population, type of government, government leader, and currency. Students answered that ASEAN promotes economic integration by implementing policies that protect local business from the pressing issues of globalization.

Drawing on insights from ASEAN 202 and 203, as well as published journals, I explained the key factors that facilitate the challenges inherent in regionalism. After the discussion, I required them to create an essay on how they understand the differences between regionalism and globalization.

“Carrie” described that ASEAN helps its member countries by implementing policies that integrate its economies. ASEAN also protects its member countries from the negative effects of globalization, which includes inequalities in economic

development and environmental degradation, and implementing tariffs on foreign countries to protect local products. ASEAN also creates policies to enhance the skills of its citizens in technology and business.

“Dezza” explained that ASEAN help its member countries to have economic integration by creating policies that improve the conditions in the industry sector, providing accessible roads for transferring goods and services, and providing accessible internet for its citizens. It also supports local businesses by providing lower taxes for local products.

“Airene” explained that ASEAN helps its member countries to have progressive and sustainable economy. Through implementing free trade, it will benefit the developing countries by competing with foreign countries.

“Julie” explained that ASEAN encourage its member countries to establish local business to provide goods and services and jobs. Through free trade agreements together with the United States and European Union, ASEAN ensures that globalization will not affect its citizens.

“Mariel” discussed that ASEAN functions as a political and economic integration to protect the interest of its member countries. It helps the developing countries to have sustainable economies, promotes cultural sensitivity by creating cultural exchanges with its member countries, and promotes Science and Technology to help its member countries innovate education and provide more secure jobs. ASEAN also implements free trade agreements as a solution for the pressing consequences of globalization.

My biggest challenge in covering ASEAN was condensing its complex concepts in one single chapter. I felt overwhelmed because I wanted to share everything I

learned in Master of ASEAN Studies, but due to limited time, and the fact that this is just a subtopic in the course “Asian Studies”. I must modify the content. I was uncertain whether my teaching approach for teaching Asian Regionalism is effective. Since I did not include interactive activities and reflective assessments, I worried that my students might have simply listened to meet course requirements rather than truly engaging in the discussion. Without concrete evidence, it was difficult to assess and evaluate their understanding.

Upon reflection, I felt my approach was too teacher-centered and had limited student engagement. I realized that the importance of incorporating student-centered approach, interactive activities and reflective assessments. It encourages students to actively participate in shaping discussions about ASEAN and allow me to better assess and evaluate their understanding. It reinforced me to expand ASEAN as a central topic in the course “Asian Studies”. I expand it into seven subtopics, which include ASEAN’s history, ASEAN core principles, ASEAN Institutional framework, Key achievements of ASEAN, ASEAN’s challenges, ASEAN External relations, and ASEAN future outlook. It utilizes culturally responsive teaching as a student-centered approach, along with interactive activities and reflective assessments to encourage students to be engaged in the discussion while assessing their own historical, cultural, and social backgrounds as Filipinos and connect of their identity as ASEAN citizens.

Daungkaew and Chongcharoen (2016) stresses the need for policy-driven approaches to enhance the effectiveness of ASEAN integration in education. Katigbak and Amante (2019) emphasize the difference between regionalism and globalization using ASEAN as example. Pasciana and Iriany (2018) added that regionalism

contributes factors to development, such as equal access to education and gender equality.

The literature (Katigbak and Amante, 2019, Pasciana and Iriany, 2018 and Daungkaew and Chongcharoen, 2016) supports my experience to include ASEAN in the broader topic of “Asian Regionalism”. I differentiate globalization and regionalism, identify the factors that lead to regional integration in ASEAN, and identify how ASEAN confront the challenges between globalization and regionalism. First, I differentiate globalization and regionalism in terms of nature, market, society and culture, humanitarian aid and technological advances. Second, I explained the reasons of Asian countries to form regional organization, such as the need for military defenses, economic crises, conservation of natural resources and protection for independence. Third, I added factors leading to regional cooperation, such as free trade and similar cultures, goals, and security needs. Last, I identified the challenges to regionalism, which includes resurgence of militant nationalism and populism, continuing financial crisis, and differing visions of regionalism. I also discussed ASEAN as an example of regional cooperation. I included its member countries, which includes Indonesia, Thailand, Malaysia, Singapore, Philippines, Cambodia, Brunei-Darussalam, Myanmar and Laos. I also presented each country’s capital, population, type of government, government leader, and currency.

Teaching the nature and concept of ASEAN as the last topic in the course syllabus by connecting their previous knowledge they learned about the history of Asia as a precursor in the foundation of ASEAN. Students can learn about ASEAN’S principles, such as non-interference, consensus-decision making and

respect for sovereignty, and see how ASEAN promotes regional cooperation and integration while effectively tackling issues through its processes and mechanisms. Students can also understand the significance of ASEAN in addressing and comprehending global and regional issues.

Figure 5. Introducing ASEAN to BSED Social Studies students

Figure 6. My discussion of ASEAN

In preparing for my course lecture, I selected fundamental yet essential topics about ASEAN that students need to understand. These include the concept and nature of ASEAN, its principles, institutional framework, external relations, key achievements and challenges, and the ASEAN Outlook 2025. The objectives include discussing the principles of ASEAN, appreciating its key achievements and challenges, and analyzing ASEAN through interactive activities.

I started with the formation of ASEAN. I explained that it was founded on August 8, 1967, when Adam Malik of Indonesia, Tun Abdul Razak of Malaysia, Narciso Ramos of the Philippines, S. Rajaratnam of Singapore and Thanat Khoman of Thailand sat down together at the main hall of the Department of Foreign Affairs building at Bangkok, Thailand and signed the ASEAN Declaration. They were called the “founding fathers” of ASEAN.

I described the colors in the ASEAN emblem, such as blue, red, and yellow represent the main colors of its member countries. Blue represents peace and stability. Red depicts courage and dynamism, white represents purity and yellow represents prosperity. I also described the stalks of padi as a symbol of ASEAN's vision to be bound together in friendship and solidarity. The circle represents unity among its member countries.

I emphasized that ASEAN is one of the most successful regional organizations in the developing world. Since 1967, ASEAN also welcomed other countries, such as Brunei (1984), Vietnam (1995), Laos (1997), Myanmar (1997), and Cambodia (1999).

Then, I discussed ASEAN's aims and objectives. It includes economic growth, social progress and cultural development through equality and partnership, promote peace and security through abiding justice and respect to the rule of law, promote active collaboration and mutual assistance for common interest, provide assistance in education and research, utilizing agriculture and industries, expansion of trade, improvement of transportation, promote Southeast Asian Studies, maintain mutual cooperation in other international or regional organizations.

In ASEAN's principles, I discussed it derived from the Treaty of Amity and Cooperation (1976). It includes respect for sovereignty, non-interference, peaceful settlement of disputes, renunciation of the use of force, and cooperation. I also elaborated the Southeast Asian History, including its pre-colonial history, the effects of colonialism, and the rising tensions during Cold War. I connected it as key factors to the formation of ASEAN.

Group 1 expanded the discussion on ASEAN's principles. I explained these based on what I learned from ASEAN 201 and 202.

In non-interference, they explained that ASEAN allows its member countries to pursue their own political systems and governance with external pressure of influence. They also contend that it hinders effective responses to the existing crises in Southeast Asia.

My students struggled to understand ASEAN because they are not familiar with the terms. I used my native language to help them learn these concepts. For example, when explaining non-interference, I translated it to Bicol language. “Dai dapat makiaram ang mga bansa sa ASEAN sa problema sa kanya-kanya nindang bansa dahil may sadiri indang batas na tigsusunod. (ASEAN countries should not interfere in each other’s internal affairs, because each has its own laws and government. It fosters mutual respect for sovereignty.)

I emphasized the importance of consensus-decision making and diplomacy in conflict resolution process. In “consensus-decision making”, even most ASEAN member countries favor a decision to address issues and concerns, if one or two ASEAN member countries opposed, the decision will be invalid.

In peaceful settlements of disputes, I explained that diplomacy encourages dialogue, negotiation and mediation for resolving conflicts and discourages the use of coercion.

In respect for sovereignty, it promotes stability by forming of East Asia Summit and ASEAN Regional Forum. It enhances political security and economic growth within Southeast Asia.

Group 2 presented the ASEAN summit as an opportunity to discuss consensus-decision making on global issues by formulating policies. They discussed ASEAN

summit, ASEAN Ministerial Meeting, ASEAN Secretariat, ASEAN Sectoral Ministerial Bodies and ASEAN Regional Forum.

ASEAN Summit serves as a platform for decision-making policy-making and decision-making processes of the leaders of ASEAN member countries. It facilitates dialogue to discuss political and security, economic and socio-cultural issues. On the other hand, the ASEAN ministerial meeting is composed by the ministers on foreign affairs of ASEAN member countries and other stakeholders to discuss issues on foreign policies, coordinate with ASEAN's external partners, reviews previous ASEAN summits, and provide recommendations for the leaders in the next ASEAN summit

They added that ASEAN Secretariat was founded in 1976 and located at Jakarta, Indonesia. They provide administrative and logistic support during ASEAN activities, such as coordinating with its member countries.

In Sectoral Ministerial Bodies, they emphasized that ASEAN was divided into three sectors, namely ASEAN Political-Security Community, ASEAN Economic Community, and ASEAN Socio-cultural Community.

In ASEAN Political-Security Community, they include ASEAN Foreign Ministers' Meeting, Commission on Southeast Asia nuclear weapon Free Zone, ASEAN Defense Ministers' Meeting, ASEAN Law Ministers' Meeting, ASEAN Ministerial Meeting on Transnational Crime, and ASEAN Regional Forum.

In ASEAN Economic Community, they include ASEAN Economic Ministers' Meeting, ASEAN Free Trade Area Council, ASEAN Investment Area Council, ASEAN Foreign Ministers' Meeting on Agriculture and Forestry, ASEAN Ministers on Energy Meeting, ASEAN Ministers' Meeting on Science and Technology, ASEAN Telecommunications and Information Technology Ministers' Meeting, ASEAN

Transport Ministers' Meeting, Meeting of the ASEAN Tourism Ministers, ASEAN Mekong Basin Development Meeting.

In ASEAN Socio-cultural Community, they include ASEAN Ministers Responsible for Information, ASEAN Ministers Responsible for Culture and Arts, ASEAN Education Ministers' Meeting, ASEAN Ministerial Meeting on Disaster Management, ASEAN Ministerial Meeting for Environment, Conference Parties to the ASEAN Agreement on Transboundary Haze Pollution, ASEAN Labor Ministers Meeting, ASEAN Ministers on Rural Development and Poverty Reduction, ASEAN Ministerial Meeting on Social Welfare and Development, ASEAN Ministerial Meeting on Youth, ASEAN Conference on Civil Service Matters.

In ASEAN Regional Forum, they discussed that it was founded in 1994. It is a platform for ASEAN members and 10 dialogue partners to address political and security issues, enhances cooperation in the Asia-Pacific Region. The 10 dialogue partners include Australia, China, India, Japan, New Zealand, South Korea, Russia, United States, Canada and the European Union.

Its objectives include fostering constructive dialogue, building confidence and diplomacy. It utilizes consensus-based decision making process.

I noticed that students were unfamiliar with some terms. I refrained from reprimanding them and instead supported their understanding. I also observed that students did their best to discuss their presentation based on the guided rubric. I also added information on the ASEAN institutional structure.

Group 3 covered ASEAN's key achievements, dividing their presentation into economic integration, socio-cultural cooperation, and disaster management and humanitarian aid. They discussed the achievement of ASEAN Free Trade Area

(AFTA) and explained by reducing trade barriers among member countries. When students asked what “tariffs” and “trade barriers” meant, I explained it in my native language for clarity. I described tariffs as “iyan sim ga dagdag na buwis kapag ang sarong bansa, gusto mag-import or export ning produkto tapos serbisyo sa ibang bansa” (additional tax imposed when a country imports or exports goods and services), and trader barriers as “iyan si mga tigpatupad kan gobyerno para magibuhan ning limitasyon ang pagtao kan produkto tapos serbisyo sa market” (government intervention to restrict the flow of goods and sweervices in the market).

In discussing “Treaty of Amity and Cooperation”, I explained that it is a pre-requisite for a Southeast Asian country to be part of ASEAN. It maintains the peace and cooperation among ASEAN member countries regardless of differences in political ideologies, economic disparities, and cultural conflicts. I used Vietnam as an example. I discussed their pre-colonial history, colonial period, Vietnam War as key factors for joining ASEAN. ASEAN in return, required Vietnam to align their interests in their objectives.

Group 4 discussed ASEAN’s challenges, which includes political and security challenges, economic challenges, and socio-cultural challenges.

In political and security challenges, it includes varying political systems, internal conflicts, decision-making challenges, South China Sea disputes, terrorism and transnational crime, territorial conflicts, and non-traditional security threats. In economic challenges, it includes uneven development, trade imbalances, and labor mobility and migration. In socio-cultural challenges, it includes deforestation and habitat loss, climate change, waste management, and marine pollution.

After their presentation, I reflect on my personal experiences in relation to the topic. During the discussion of internal conflicts, I shared my personal experience watching TikTok videos during Myanmar's 2021 coup, reflecting on the anxiety caused by the situation amid the Covid-19 pandemic. I connected these conflicts with consensus decision-making challenges, explaining that it delays resolutions. I also explained that ASEAN experiences difficulties in economic integration because of its member countries' economic inequalities.

In labor mobility and migration, I explained that Overseas Filipino Workers decided to work abroad because of better income and opportunities. In discussing security tensions, I emphasized the role of ASEAN in addressing the pressing issue with China. ASEAN requested to China for having dialogues, but China didn't recognize it. On terrorism and transnational crime, I used the term "Islamic Fundamentalism" to clarify that these groups interpret Islamic teachings strictly and reject western ideologies. They have different interpretations in Quran. I compared it to Christianity and emphasize that Christians have different interpretations of the bible. I also stress how various religion shapes culture in Southeast Asia, stressing the need for mutual respect for diverse belief systems.

In discussing territorial conflict, I explained that religion was one of the reasons for having territorial disputes in ASEAN. Pattani was a former part of Thailand but because of war, it became a part of Malaysia. Thailand and Malaysia have different culture. Malaysia implemented strict regulations in Pattani, including conversion of Islam. However, the natives of Pattani resisted because of their devotion to Buddhism, resulting in oppression. Thai nationals were also affected. The Thai government decided to attack Pattani to rescue them, which resulted to territorial conflict.

For discussing deforestation and habitat loss, I emphasize kaingin farming as a common practice in the Philippines and other Southeast Asian countries. I also explain the effects of climate change, such as rising sea levels and calamities such as flash floods and landslides, using my personal experience with the typhoon “Kristine” in Bicol. The group emphasized the effects of development for having pollution. It stresses the need for solid waste management.

Group 5 discusses ASEAN External Relations. They emphasized that China is the largest trade partner of ASEAN. “Belt and Road Initiative” provide opportunities for infrastructure development in ASEAN but has high interest rates that could lead to debt.

United States is the main partner of ASEAN for security cooperation and counter-terrorism efforts. They are also trade partners of ASEAN through Indo-Pacific Economic Framework.

Japan is the main partner of ASEAN for disaster management and infrastructure efforts. They are also trade partners of ASEAN through ASEAN-Japan Free Trade Agreement. India is also a trade partner of ASEAN through ASEAN-India Free Trade Agreement.

They also emphasized other mechanisms in ASEAN. It includes ASEAN Plus Three and Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation. ASEAN Plus Three is a mechanism composed of ASEAN and China, Japan and South Korea to promote economic growth, political stability, and effective disaster response. Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation is a mechanism that focuses on Economic Development.

After their presentation, I added that the importance of ASEAN Plus Three in economic integration includes improving communication, investment, trade

frameworks, financial stability, infrastructure and supply chains. I also explained that APEC has similar goals to ASEAN Economic Integration. However, APEC was focused on Asia-Pacific region.

Group 6 discusses ASEAN Vision 2025. I emphasized that this is a continuation of previous ASEAN roadmaps, focusing on development and integration efforts from 2016 to 2025.

Katigbak and Amante (2019) found that incorporating ASEAN in higher education promotes regional cooperation and integration. It supports my initiative to include ASEAN as a central topic in the course Asian Studies. It includes ASEAN core principles, ASEAN institutional frameworks, key achievements of ASEAN and ASEAN challenges, ASEAN external relations and ASEAN future outlook.

In ASEAN's core principles, it includes non-interference, consensus-based decision making, peaceful settlement of disputes and respect for sovereignty.

In ASEAN's institutional frameworks, it includes the ASEAN summit, ASEAN ministerial meeting, ASEAN secretariat, sectorial ministerial bodies, such as ASEAN political-security community, ASEAN economic community and ASEAN socio-cultural community, and ASEAN regional forum.

In key achievements of ASEAN, it divides into four categories. The first category is economic integration, which includes ASEAN Economic Community and the ASEAN Free Trade Area. The second category is promoting peace and security, which includes Treaty of Amity and Cooperation, East Asia Summit, ASEAN Regional Forum, ASEAN Defense Ministers Meeting Plus. The third category is socio-cultural cooperation, which includes ASEAN Socio-cultural Community. The fourth category is

Disaster Management and Humanitarian Aid which includes ASEAN Agreement on Disaster Management and Emergency Response.

In ASEAN's challenges, it includes political diversity, economic disparities, security tensions and environmental issues.

In ASEAN's external relations, it is divided into two categories. The first category is ASEAN and major powers, which includes China, Japan, United States of America, and India. The second category is ASEAN regional dialogue and multicultural engagement, which includes ASEAN Plus Three (China, Japan, South Korea), Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership, and Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation.

In ASEAN future outlook, it is divided into four categories. The first category is the ASEAN Community Vision 2025, which includes ASEAN Political-security Community, ASEAN Economic Community, and ASEAN Socio-cultural Community. Other categories include Covid-19 pandemic recovery, climate change and sustainability and regional cooperation.

Karatas (2020) emphasizes the importance of culturally responsive teaching in making complex concepts, such as ASEAN, more comprehensible by incorporating students' languages, culture, and lived experiences. Cawaling-Mauntol and Padua (2022) added that educators should empower students to engage with dialogue to bridge cultural gaps.

It supports my initiative to connect theoretical knowledge and real-life experiences such as using bikol as native language to help them understand ASEAN's principles, using real-life examples and connecting them to their personal experiences, such as the flash floods in the Bicol region associated with Typhoon Kristine. I also

mentioned ASEANs varied political and cultural tensions, such as the “Islamic Fundamentalism”. I help the students to understand that their community has different interpretations of Qur’an.

These initiatives helps them validate their identities and backgrounds as ASEAN citizens and apply their learning when they become future educators.

Teaching students to research and present their assigned topics on ASEAN with course guidelines and rubric

Figure 7. Research activity with assigned topics on ASEAN with course guidelines and rubrics (page 1)

Commission on Higher Education
CALABANGA COMMUNITY COLLEGE
Belen, Calabanga, Camarines Sur

MCSSE 12 ASIAN STUDIES
1ST SEMESTER AY 2024-2025
ASYNCHRONOUS ACTIVITY

INSTRUCTIONS:

1. Search from the following topics below.
2. Make a powerpoint presentation of the topics.
3. You will report the topics in front of the class. The report must include motivational activities and processing questions.

GROUP 1: ASEAN's Core Principles

1. Non-Interference
2. Consensus-Based Decision Making
3. Peaceful Settlement of Disputes
4. Respect for Regional and Global Stability

GROUP 2: ASEAN's Institutional Structure

1. The ASEAN Summit
2. The ASEAN Ministerial Meeting (AMM)
3. The ASEAN Secretariat
4. Sectoral Ministerial Bodies
5. ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF)

GROUP 3: Key Achievements of ASEAN

1. Economic Integration:
 - a. ASEAN Free Trade Area (AFTA)
 - b. The ASEAN Economic Community (AEC)
2. Promoting Peace and Stability:
 - a. Treaty of Amity and Cooperation (TAC)
 - b. East Asia Summit (EAS)
 - c. ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF)
 - d. ASEAN Defense Ministers' Meeting Plus (ADMM-Plus)

Figure 8. Research activity with assigned topics on ASEAN with course guidelines and rubrics (page 2)

3. Social and Cultural Cooperation
 - a. ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community (ASCC)
4. Disaster Management and Humanitarian Aid:
 - a. ASEAN Agreement on Disaster Management and Emergency Response (AADMER)

GROUP 4: ASEAN's Challenges

1. Political Diversity
2. Economic Disparities
3. Security Tensions
4. Environmental and Sustainability Issues:

GROUP 5: ASEAN's External Relations

1. ASEAN and Major Powers:
 - a. China
 - b. United States
 - c. Japan
 - d. India
2. ASEAN Regional Dialogue and Multilateral Engagement:
 - a. ASEAN Plus Three (China, Japan, and South Korea)
 - b. Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP)
 - c. Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC)

GROUP 6: ASEAN's Future Outlook

1. Vision 2025 and Beyond
 - a. The ASEAN Community Vision 2025
 - b. ASEAN Political-Security Community (APSC), ASEAN Economic Community (AEC), and ASEAN Socio-Cultural Community (ASCC).
2. Post-Pandemic Recovery
3. Climate Change and Sustainability
4. Regional Security Cooperation

Figure 9. Research activity with assigned topics on ASEAN with course guidelines and rubrics (page 3)

RUBRIC:

Category	Excellent (4)	Good (3)	Satisfactory (2)	Needs Improvement (1)
Content Accuracy & Depth	Thorough, accurate content with excellent depth and insight.	Content is mostly accurate with good depth.	Content is generally accurate but lacks depth or clarity.	Content has no depth and clarity.
Organization & Structure	Clear, logical flow; introduction, body, and conclusion are well-structured.	Mostly clear organization, but minor issues with flow.	Organization is somewhat unclear; some sections lack smooth transitions.	Content has uncleaned and no transitions.
Visual Aids (Slides, etc.)	Highly effective, clear, and professional; enhances understanding.	Visual aids are effective and clear, with minor issues.	Visual aids are basic and occasionally unclear or distracting.	Content is uncleaned and distracting.
Delivery (Clarity, Pace, Confidence)	Clear, confident, well-paced delivery; excellent eye contact.	Clear delivery with good pace and mostly confident.	Delivery is somewhat unclear or lacks confidence.	Delivery is unclear and has no confidence.
Engagement & Interaction	Actively engages audience with questions, eye contact, or discussion.	Some audience engagement, but not consistent.	Limited engagement, mainly speaking to slides.	Has no engagement in the discussion
Time Management	Excellent use of time; presentation stays within allotted time.	Generally good time management, with minor over/under time issues.	Some time management issues; presentation too short/long.	Has management issues during the discussion.
Creativity & Originality	Highly creative and original; presentation stands out.	Some creativity and original ideas are evident.	Minimal creativity; relies heavily on standard approaches.	Has no creativity and originality in the discussion.

Total possible score = 40 points.

Final Score: ___ / 40

Prepared by:

CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA

Instructor

After I discussed the concept and nature of ASEAN, I divided the class into six groups, and each group will do research on their assigned topics. They should create Powerpoint Presentation and present their findings in class. Each group is required to include motivational activities and processing questions, and rubric.

Karatas (2020) found that culturally responsive teaching creates inclusive learning environments. It promotes creativity to help students take their ownership in learning. Birru (2024) identifies collaborative learning strategies such as groupwork enhances 21st century skills. Garba et. al. (20215) added that integrating ICT tools enhances information and communication technology skills.

It supports my initiative to create an activity with guidelines and rubrics. I divide the class into six groups, and each groups research and creates presentation based on their assigned topics. It includes ASEAN's core principles (group 1), ASEAN Institutional Structure (group 2), Key achievements of ASEAN (group 3), ASEAN challenges (group 4), ASEAN External relations (group 5) and ASEAN future outlook (group 6). In rubrics, I included content accuracy and depth, organization and structure, utilization of visual aids, content delivery, time management, engagement and interaction, and creativity and originality. Using likert scale such 4 (excellent), 3 (good), 2 (satisfactory) and 1 (needs improvement) provides fairness in assessing their knowledge and skills in a holistic manner.

Teaching the contribution and significance of ASEAN in the course titled “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics by engaging on ASEAN personally, presenting their analysis to meet academic standards,

Figure 12. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 3)

Bibliography:

1. _____

2. _____

3. _____

4. Can you share any personal or familial stories that highlight the diverse ancestry present in your community? Describe how these stories contribute to your sense of identity.

Bibliography:

1. _____

Figure 13. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 4)

2. _____

3. _____

5. What cultural practices and traditions do you believe are unique to Filipinos within the ASEAN community? Discuss any specific festivals, rituals, or customs that you think are significant.

Bibliography:

1. _____

2. _____

3. _____

6. How do you see these cultural practices evolving in response to regional influences from other ASEAN countries? Provide examples of how cultural exchange has affected Filipino traditions.

Figure 15. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 6)

3. _____

8. In what ways do you think regional differences impact educational practices or social interactions within ASEAN? Reflect on any experiences that illustrate these impacts.

Bibliography:

1. _____

2. _____

3. _____

9. What does collective identity mean to you as a member of the ASEAN community? Discuss how you believe shared values or experiences contribute to this collective identity.

Figure 18. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 9)

RUBRIC

Criteria	Excellent (4)	Proficient (3)	Satisfactory (2)	Needs Improvement (1)
Content and Ideas	Demonstrates a deep understanding of ASEAN's significance, principles, and impact; provides insightful and well-supported reflections.	Shows a good understanding of ASEAN's importance with relevant reflections and examples.	Demonstrates basic understanding of ASEAN; reflections lack depth or examples.	Lacks understanding of ASEAN; reflections are unclear, unsupported, or off-topic.
Organization	Essay has a clear and logical structure with an engaging introduction, well-developed body, and strong conclusion.	Essay is well-organized, but transitions between sections could be smoother.	Essay has a basic structure but lacks coherence in some parts or misses key sections.	Essay lacks clear organization; ideas are disjointed or difficult to follow.
Critical Thinking	Demonstrates exceptional critical thinking by analyzing ASEAN's impact on global and local contexts.	Shows good critical thinking by discussing ASEAN's relevance but lacks deeper analysis.	Basic analysis is present but lacks connections or depth in exploring ASEAN's impact.	Limited or no evidence of critical thinking about ASEAN's relevance or impact.
Relevance and Reflection	Insights are highly relevant and demonstrate personal connections to ASEAN's themes or principles.	Reflections are relevant but personal connections are less emphasized.	Reflections are somewhat relevant but lack clear personal connections or insights.	Reflections are irrelevant or show little to no personal engagement.

Figure 19. My final examination about the contribution of ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through the use of course guidelines and rubrics (page 10)

Language and Mechanics	Writing is fluent, error-free, and uses precise vocabulary appropriate for the topic.	Writing is clear with minor errors that do not detract from readability.	Writing contains several errors that slightly impact readability or professionalism.	Writing has numerous errors that significantly affect understanding or presentation.
Use of Examples	Provides well-chosen and detailed examples to support reflections and analysis.	Includes relevant examples but lacks depth or variety.	Uses few or generic examples with minimal connection to the reflections.	Lacks examples or uses irrelevant examples.
Creativity and Engagement	Demonstrates originality and presents reflections in a highly engaging manner.	Shows some creativity and maintains the reader’s interest.	Somewhat engaging, but lacks originality or creativity in presentation.	Reflection is unoriginal and fails to engage the reader.

Scoring Guide:

- **28–24:** Excellent (A)
- **23–20:** Proficient (B)
- **19–16:** Satisfactory (C)
- **15 and below:** Needs Improvement (D/F)

Prepared by:

CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA
Instructor

I designed a reflection assessment to encourage my students to explore their positionalities as Filipinos within their identities as ASEAN citizens. The only guideline is a strict prohibition of plagiarism and the use of Artificial intelligence. The assessment is structure around four concepts, based on Milner's (2007) framework. It includes (1) examining students' cultural, racial, and historical backgrounds; (2) reflecting on how these backgrounds shape their positionalities; (3) examining their positionalities on race and culture within society, and how they navigate tensions in their beliefs; and (4) analyzing past and present social, political and historical factors that influence their racial and cultural backgrounds.

The first concept includes questions 1, question 2, question 3, and question 4. The second concept includes question 5 and question 6. The third concept includes question 7 and question 8. The fourth concept includes question 9 and question 10.

In question 1, students answered that ethno-racial identity can foster cultural awareness through respecting each other's' belief and practices. However, Group 3 and group 4 argued that the effects of colonization and pressing issues of globalization were found to be the hindrances in preserving ethno-racial identity.

In question 2, students answered that the effect of colonization helps them to interact with the foreigners. Through shared cultures such as understanding different cuisines, it helps them to respect diversity. However, group 6 argued that language barriers were found to be a hindrance to interact with the foreigners.

In question 3, students defined "diverse ancestry" as cultural identity that was adapted and passed through different generations. It is observed through languages and cultural practices such as traditions. Group 5 added that pre-colonial trade and

migration by arabs, Indians, and Chinese, and colonization by western powers were found to be factors in shaping their diverse ancestry.

In question 4, students answered that family stories help them connect experience to present realities. It includes religious practices (devotion to Our Lady of La Porteria) and oral literature about indigenous legends (Daragang Mayon).

In question 5, students distinguished traits that are unique to the Filipinos within ASEAN community, such as “bayanihan”, “pakikisama”, and the use of “po” and “opo” as courtesy to elders. However, spanish colonization influenced their cultural practices, such as celebrating Penafrancia Festival as one of their traditions.

In question 6, students answered exploring the taste of different cuisines, appreciate different music, and the use of English language for communication helps them respond to the evolving influences of ASEAN countries in their everyday life.

In question 7, students perceived religion in shaping cultural practices, such as celebrating festivals, understanding different cuisines, and using their native language for communication and education.

In question 8, students explained that ASEAN countries address their social gaps through education. It includes integrating religion and history into education to build sense of identity. Group 1 added strengthening Science and Technology in education system in Singapore, ASEAN integration in education in Thailand, and integrating English language in education in the Philippines.

In question 9, students defined “collective identity” as sense of belonging and mutual respect among people in terms of history and culture, including practices, traditions and norms. It helps students understand the cultural similarities and differences within ASEAN community.

In question 10, students answered that integrating ASEAN into the curriculum to help students understand diversity within ASEAN community. They also recommend that teachers should foster inclusivity by identifying the racial and cultural backgrounds of students, contextualizing teaching approaches and adapting localized content.

Cawaling-Mauntol and Padua (2022) emphasize the importance of culturally responsive teaching to help the students identify their positionalities. Pasciana and Iriany, (2018), added that culturally responsive teaching serves as socio-political lens for understanding the political, cultural, and historical factors in shaping cultural identity. It supports my initiative to utilize Milner's (2007) framework in promoting students' positionalities as Filipinos and connect to their identities as ASEAN citizens.

Karatas (2020) added that it helps students to recognize their experiences and enhance understanding of their historical, cultural and social backgrounds. It supports the first part of my reflective assessment, which includes question 1, question 2, question 3 and question 4. " These questions help students explore their cultural, historical and social backgrounds to recognize their privileges and biases, foster mutual respect by appreciating cultural similarities and differences, encourage storytelling to reveal hidden stories and reconstruct marginalized narratives, and reveal gaps in understanding uncomfortable truths about diverse ancestry and sense of identity and belonging.

Karatas observe that students' backgrounds shape their perceptions and interactions. It supports the second part of my reflective assessment, where BSED social Studies students reflect on their cultural, historical, and social perspectives that shape their experiences. It includes question 5 and question 6. The questions

encourage students to appreciate the unique traits of Filipinos compare to other ASEAN countries and strengthen their national pride. It also highlights how globalization and regionalism influence local traditions.

Karatas stresses the need to recognize and confront historical, cultural and social tensions. It supports the third part of my reflective assessment, which encourages BSED Social Studies students to evaluate their cultural, historical and and question 8. These questions help students to reflect how their own biases and assumptions affects their understanding of diversity by recognizing variations of culture among ASEAN community while acknowledging their unique identities as Filipinos.

Karatas stresses the contextualization of students' identities based on cultural, historical, and social frameworks. It supports the fourth part of my reflective assessment, which helps students to relate their historical, cultural and social background to the existing social system where they live. It includes question 9 and question 10 "How can educators foster collective identity among students with diverse backgrounds within ASEAN? Share ideas that could enhance understanding among students".

These questions help students reflect on their positionality as future educators to connect theoretical knowledge and real-life experiences. Karatas (2020) and Cawaling-Mauntol and Padua (2022) found that reflective assessments bridge theoretical knowledge with real-life experiences to enhance regional awareness.

Requiring the students to showcase the nation and cultural identity of ASEAN member countries and its neighboring countries through creative methods and

integrating different disciplines through similarities of culture in food, attire, government system, and flag

Figure 20. My guidelines on culminating activity

Commission on Higher Education
CALABANGA COMMUNITY COLLEGE
Belen, Calabanga, Camarines Sur

MCSSE 12 ASIAN STUDIES
FINAL EXAMINATION FOR THE 1ST SEMESTER 2022-2023

I. Instruction:

The class will do a final examination called "Asian Nations Parade," which aims to celebrate and showcase the diverse cultures of Asia, particularly Southeast Asia.

II. Activity Guidelines:

1. Each student will choose one country from Southeast Asia or its neighboring regions. Ensure no two or more students choose the same country to avoid duplication.
2. Prepare a brief presentation about the selected country and include the following basic information: Country name and location should highlight its place on the map. Provide general statistics on population and languages, and discuss one or two cultural aspects like traditions, festivals, or attire.
3. Prepare a popular dish or snack from the selected country. Describe the ingredients and how the dish is made. Explain the historical or cultural significance of the food in the chosen country.
4. During the presentations, students should wear traditional attire from their chosen country.

III. Judging Criteria:

- **Content Quality (50 points):** Accuracy and depth of information about the country and food.
- **Creativity (30 points):** Visual presentation, costumes, and enthusiasm during the parade.
- **Food Connection (20 points):** Clear explanation of the dish's cultural ties to other Asian nations.
- Students must submit their chosen country by November 25, 2022.
- The activity will be on the first of annuary, 2023.

After exploring key topics in “Asian Studies”, I decided to create a final project that celebrate and showcase the rich cultural diversity of ASEAN and its neighboring countries. The “Asian Nations Parade” aims to deepen students’ appreciation of the culture, geography, and cuisine of their Southeast Asia and its neighboring countries. Each student chooses country from Southeast Asia or neighboring country. Then, students should prepare a presentation which includes population and languages, traditions, festivals, clothing. Students were encouraged to use visuals such as posters, slides, or traditional costumes. Students also prepared cuisine from their selected countries. They require to describe its ingredients, how it was made, and its historical or cultural significance.

In evaluating presentations, students were evaluated through content quality (50 points), creativity (30 points), and food connection (20 points).

The activity began at 2:00 pm with an opening prayer led by my students. It followed by the opening remarks by me as their instructor. I express my gratitude for their effort and dedication to making the activity successful. I announced that the activity was part of their final project in the course Asian Studies.

The next part of the project was the presentation. Each student has 15 minutes to showcase their represented country, including their attire and cuisine. The presentation lasted two hours. The activity fosters respect for diversity and cultural competence. It allows students to apply their knowledge in practical and meaningful ways.

I also discovered that experiential learning enables students to apply their knowledge in real-life applications and reinforce students to take their ownership by

allowing them to contextualize their design, choose cuisines, and present their output in meaningful ways.

After the culminating activity, I required my students to submit a position paper to share their experiences and thoughts.

“Zyra” explained that religion influenced Filipino moral values, which shaped the celebration of festivals and other practices. She distinguished “Pakikisama” as a unique of the Filipinos apart than ASEAN and neighboring countries.

“Shamen” realized that religion shaped cultural practices in Asian countries. “Fidel” examined how religion shaped government systems in Southeast Asia and its neighboring countries.

“Hazel” described the similarities how trade can be a key factor for sharing cultural practices in ASEAN. “Diana” discussed the similarities of ASEAN countries in terms of culture, such as native language and religious practices

“Melvin” explained the development of ASEAN and neighboring countries after colonialism. “Ish” realized the advantages and disadvantages of globalization in the agricultural sector in Southeast Asia. “Erika” discussed the effects of globalization in providing goods and services but can affect culture. “Joy” discussed the importance of tourism to showcase various places and landscapes in Southeast Asia.

“Angelyn” discussed how cultural identity is a key factor on how globalization enhance agriculture and transportation sector in Southeast Asia.

Out of twenty-four students, only fourteen students submitted. I was disappointed because some didn’t know how to make position paper, while others

didn't follow instructions. They admit that they were still affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, and they still didn't know how to use internet resources properly.

As I reflected in my teaching experience, I learned that most students decided to learn knowledge and skills but didn't have similar privileges. It will be difficult for them if I still be firm on strict rules. I should change my approach to teaching students. I should also identify their backgrounds to consider their situation.

I should also be an inspiration for them to succeed in their academic journey. College is just a starting point for them to learn. As a teacher, I guide them in transferring knowledge and help them learn 21st century skills. It will be a moral lesson for me to refine my teaching practices next school year. It should be specific, measurable, attainable, resourceful, and time bound for my students.

Katigbak and Amante (2019) asserts that education enhances 21st century skills and functions as a powerful tool for cultivating ASEAN identity among member states. Experiential learning examines the diverse cultures of Southeast Asia and neighboring countries through understanding traditions, geography and cuisines and promote regional awareness. It supports my initiative to conduct culminating activity with guidelines and rubrics. In guidelines, I allowed my students to choose their country they want to represent, to be creative in presenting their languages, populations, festivals, and clothing, and to be resourceful in finding their cuisines. In rubric, I choose content quality, creativity and food connection to help students construct new knowledge.

Karatas (2020) and Cawaling-Mauntol and Padua (2022) suggest that integrating students' cultural backgrounds increase cultural awareness by appreciating students' positionalities and identities. It supports my initiative to

encourage BSED Social Studies to explore ASEAN identity in a holistic manner. Students answered that ASEAN community has shared cultures in terms of native languages and religion. They emphasized that religion shaped cultural practices, such as celebrating festivals and traditions, as well as understanding different government systems. They also emphasized that Philippines has distinct traits from other ASEAN member countries, such as the concept of “pakikisama” or sense of belonging for everyone. They also found that globalization can affect the preservation of cultures.

These answers help students understand how regional cooperation preserves cultural heritage while respecting diversity.

Higher Education Teachers’ Perspectives in Incorporating Asean In Teaching Social Studies

ASEAN has to be appreciated by the students that may help build ASEAN identity

I chose this study to explore innovative approaches to teaching ASEAN in higher education and propose to school administrators, policymakers, and other members of the school community. It includes a reformed curriculum based on my firsthand experience on incorporating ASEAN into the BSED Social Studies program. It is also my way of advocating ASEAN in Calabanga Community College to help my students appreciate ASEAN as both a political and economic organization and a framework for shared regional identity.

My initiative includes the annual revisions of my course syllabus. In my first year of teaching, I include ASEAN as a culminating activity in the course Asian Studies. In my second year of teaching, I include ASEAN as a subtopic in the broader topic of “Asian Regionalism” in the course Asian Studies. In my third year of teaching, I include ASEAN as a central theme in the course Asian Studies.

This revision was based on my teaching experiences. In my first year of teaching, I viewed ASEAN as a supplemental information in Asian Studies course. However, when students shared their learnings about the importance the respect for diversity and cultural competence through position paper, I realized that I should advocate ASEAN in terms of its mechanisms and processes to help the students understand the role of ASEAN not only a political and economic organization, but a framework for promoting regional identity.

This experience provides me perspective to revise the course syllabus and add ASEAN as a subtopic in the broader topic of “Asian Regionalism” in my second year of teaching. I utilized teacher-centered approach to discuss the difference between globalization and regionalism, explain the reasons of Asian countries in forming regional organization, add factors leading to regional cooperation, and identify the challenges to regionalism. Then I used ASEAN as an example of regional organization in Asia. However, given its complex nature, I experienced difficulties emphasizing ASEAN because it was compressing and lack of student engagement.

This experience provides me with a perspective to revise the course syllabus in my third year of teaching. I include seven subtopics which include the history of ASEAN, ASEAN core principles, ASEAN Institutional key achievements and

challenges of ASEAN, structure, ASEAN external relations, and ASEAN look forward 2025.

I also recognized the importance of promoting cultural awareness. It prompts me to utilize culturally responsive teaching as student-centered approach, utilize interactive activities, reflective assessment using Milner's (2007) framework. It helps BSED social Studies to be engaged in the learning process, while reflecting on their positionalities as Filipinos, and connect to their identities as ASEAN citizens. With the skills that I learned from studying Master of ASEAN Studies, and with the support of school administration to allow me to integrate ASEAN in course syllabus, these experiences provide me with a perspective to promote ASEAN in the most possible way that I can do.

Katigbak and Amante (2019) emphasized the role of higher education institutions in promoting ASEAN identity among its students. Daungkaew and Chongcharoen (2016) added that higher education institutions should create policies which align with the ASEAN Economic Community. It includes languages, cultures and histories to enhance students' knowledge and understanding about ASEAN.

This literature supports the inclusion of ASEAN in the course "Asian Studies". In the first year of my teaching experience, I include ASEAN as culminating activity to explore the interconnection of ASEAN countries in terms of culture, history, and trade, in second year of my teaching experience, I include ASEAN as a subtopic in the broader topic of "Asian Regionalism" to differentiate regionalism from globalization, explain the reasons of Asian countries in forming regional organization, add factors leading to regional cooperation, and identify the challenges to regionalism, and in my third year of my teaching experience, I include ASEAN as a central topic in the course

syllabus and has seven subtopics which include the history of ASEAN, ASEAN core principles, ASEAN Institutional key achievements and challenges of ASEAN, structure, ASEAN external relations, and ASEAN look forward 2025. It enables students to understand the role of ASEAN not only a political and economic organization but a framework for shared regional identity.

BSED Social Studies students as future educators should have a deep appreciation and commitment and effort of ASEAN to achieve regional cooperation among its member countries

I am the only student pursuing Master of ASEAN Studies while simultaneously working as a teacher at Calabanga Community College. In addition, I am teaching a course titled “Asian Studies” in the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) major in Social Studies program. This background provides me with an opportunity to promote ASEAN studies in higher education, by including ASEAN in course lectures.

I also valued the importance of choosing an approach in teaching regional cooperation and integration. I compared the similarities and differences between utilizing teacher-centered and student-centered approaches in teaching ASEAN to BSED Social Studies students. Based on my teaching experiences, I learned that teacher-centered approach lacks student engagement. On the other hand, student-centered approach empowers the role of the teachers as a facilitator of constructing knowledge, and enhances 21st century skills such as communication, creativity, collaboration, and critical-thinking skills. It also promotes the use of ICT tools for making outputs.

It helps me to teach them to become advocates of regionalism by becoming future educators. It also demonstrates that local higher education institutions, such as Calabanga Community College, can deliver quality education similarly to public and private universities.

Katigbak and Amante (2019) argue that teachers can include ASEAN in the curriculum to address regional and local needs. Daungkaew and Chongcharoen (2016) added that institutional support improves teaching competencies and promotes inclusive education.

It resonates my efforts to incorporate ASEAN into the course “Asian Studies” under Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) major in Social Studies program at Calabanga Community College. Since I am the only student pursuing Master of ASEAN Studies and simultaneously as a teacher at Calabanga Community College, it provides an opportunity to promote ASEAN studies by including ASEAN in course lectures.

My teaching experiences also helped me choose effective teaching approaches and strategies in teaching BSED Social Studies students to advocate regional cooperation when they become future educators.

Respect for diversity and cultural competence to develop regional citizenship

I explored different learning strategies, which include culminating activity to help BSED Social Studies students understand the importance of sensitivity in dealing people with diverse cultures. It offers a unique perspective that sets them apart from the prototype course syllabus and represents an opportunity for me to guide the students to transform themselves into ASEAN citizens.

However, it presents a significant challenge for me, as I am the only one taking this initiative at Calabanga Community College. Since I experienced lack of resources on how I incorporated ASEAN in my teaching. I allowed my students to be creative in their attire. I also encouraged them to choose cuisines that are available in the marketplace, such as Shawarma, Siomai, Siopao, Pancit, Soju, as well as others.

Heryadi et. al. (2019) observed that many higher education institutions lack resources and institutional support, which hinders student engagement. Similarly, Birru (2024) stresses the responsibility of educators in integrating 21st century skills to meet global standards.

The literature (Heryadi, et. al., 2019, Garba et. al, 2015) supports my experience in teaching ASEAN, such as lack of resources and institutional support. Despite this, I created guidelines and guided rubrics which allow the BSED Social Studies students to be creative in presenting their outputs using local resources to make the culminating activity successful. I also integrate ICT Tools to help them improve 21st century skills.

Relationship between practices and perspectives

There is a dynamic relationship between my teaching practices and perspectives. My teaching experience influences how I create my teaching practices to respond to the various needs of BSED Social studies students.

I observed that ASEAN was not included in the prototype course syllabus. As a student of Master of ASEAN Studies, It provides me an opportunity to help students appreciate ASEAN for building regional identity. It prompted me to include ASEAN in the course syllabus, which includes ASEAN as a culminating activity, ASEAN as a

subtopic in the broader topic of “Asian Regionalism”, and ASEAN as a central topic in the course “Asian Studies”.

In my first year of teaching, I include ASEAN in the course “Asian Studies” through culminating activity to promote respect for diversity and cultural competence. It helps me to promote inclusivity. However, I realized that BSED Social Studies students, as future educators, need to learn the role of ASEAN not as a political and economic organization but as a framework for promoting regional identity.

It prompted me to include ASEAN as a subtopic in the broader topic of “Asian Regionalism” in my second year of teaching, which includes differentiating regionalism from globalization, explaining the reasons of Asian countries in forming regional organization, and identifying factors leading to regional cooperation and challenges to regionalism. I utilized teacher-centered approach assuming it would be effective. However, the result was not effective because of time constraints and lacks engagement.

It prompted me to revise the course syllabus and change my approach in my third year of my teaching .I include ASEAN as a central topic in the course syllabus and has seven subtopics which include the history of ASEAN, ASEAN core principles, ASEAN Institutional key achievements and challenges of ASEAN, structure, ASEAN external relations, and ASEAN look forward 2025. I utilized culturally responsive teaching as a student-centered approach with interactive activities and reflective assessments such as Milner’s (2007) framework.

It helps students to develop that integrate 21st century skills and reflect to their positionalities as Filipinos and connect to their identity as ASEAN citizens. It also

enables students to understand the role of ASEAN not only a political and economic organization but a framework for shared regional identity.

CHAPTER VI

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents a summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results.

Research Questions

1. What are the higher education teacher's practices in incorporating ASEAN in teaching Social Studies?
2. What are the perspectives that underlies the higher education teacher's practices for integrating ASEAN in teaching Social Studies?

Research Framework

My research framework is autoethnography and autoethnomethodology. Autoethnography allows me to examine my teaching experiences and perspectives for incorporating ASEAN in higher education. On the other hand, autoethnomethodology allows me to identify teaching practices for integrating ASEAN in teaching BSED Social Studies.

Research Methodology

As both the research the subject and researcher, it employs reflective narratives, critical self-inquiry and curriculum analysis. The data sources include course syllabus, course lectures, and course assessments.

Results

In the higher education teacher's practice in incorporating ASEAN in teaching Social Studies, it includes (a) including selected topics about on the course titled "Asian Studies", focusing on the interconnection of ASEAN countries in terms of culture, history, and trade; explain the regional dynamics of Asia within economic, political and cultural contexts; and understand the nature and concept of ASEAN, (b) incorporating ASEAN in teaching the topic "Asian Regionalism", which the final topic in the course "Asian Studies", and covers the difference between globalization and regionalization, along with benefits and challenges, (c) teaching the nature and concept of ASEAN, including principles of ASEAN as the last topic in the course syllabus by connecting their previous knowledge they learned about the history of Asia as a precursor in the foundation of ASEAN (d) teaching students to research and present their assigned topics on ASEAN with course guidelines and rubrics, (e) requiring the students to showcase the nation and cultural identity of ASEAN member countries and its neighboring countries through creative methods and integrating different disciplines through similarities of culture in food, attire, government system, and flag, and (f) teaching the contribution and significance of ASEAN in the course titled "Asian Studies" through the use of course guidelines and rubrics by engaging on ASEAN personally, presenting their analysis to meet academic standards, evaluating

their comprehension of ASEAN as a concept, and applying these concepts to Asian Regionalism to real-life scenarios.

In the higher education teachers' perspectives in incorporating ASEAN in teaching social studies, it includes ASEAN has to be appreciated by the students that may help build ASEAN identity, BSED Social Studies students as future educators should have a deep appreciation and commitment and effort of ASEAN to achieve regional cooperation among its member countries and respect for diversity and cultural competence to develop regional citizenship

Contribution To Aseanology

The results positively impact ASEANOLOGY in higher education. First, the inclusion of ASEAN in the course syllabus as culminating activity, as a subtopic in the broader topic of "Asian Regionalism" and as a central topic in the course syllabus in Asian Studies helps students learn that the Philippines is an integral part of ASEAN and help build their identity as ASEAN citizens.

Second, Filipino educators have the responsibility to teach students the role of ASEAN in strengthening regional cooperation through learning the difference between regionalism from globalization, explaining the reasons of Asian countries in forming regional organization, identifying factors leading to regional cooperation and its challenges, and the history of ASEAN, ASEAN core principles, ASEAN Institutional key achievements and challenges of ASEAN, structure, ASEAN external relations, and ASEAN look forward 2025 through different teaching approaches and strategies.

Last, promoting respect for diversity and cultural competence within ASEAN community through experiential learning such as culminating activity makes ASEAN

more meaningful beyond traditional textbooks. It emphasizes the role of ASEAN not only as a political and economic organization but also as a framework for regional identity.

Recommendations

1. Higher education institutions should open educational resources (OER) provide training and workshops to create specialized modules focused on ASEAN.
2. Higher education institutions should provide scholarships for those people who want to pursue continuing education in ASEAN.
3. Encourage school-wide interactive activities to help students appreciate ASEAN beyond traditional teaching approaches.
4. Curriculum innovations should be aligned with the CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 75, series of 2017 to meet educational standards.

REFERENCES

a. Journal with multiple authors

Cawaling-Mauntol, J., & Padua, S. A. (2022). **Uncovering diversity in social studies through culturally responsive pedagogy among indigenous students in the Philippines.** *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2(12), 88–104. <https://www.ijams-bbp.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/1-IJAMS-December-88-104.pdf>

Daungkaew, R., & Chongcharoen, K. (2016). **Higher education policies in promoting ASEAN Community in Thailand.** In Proceedings of IAC 2016. Czech Institute of Academic Education. <https://doi.org/10.20472/IAC.2016.023.033>

Garba, S. A., Byabazaire, Y., & Busthami, A. H. (2015). **Toward the use of 21st century teaching-learning approaches: The trend of development in Malaysian schools within the context of Asia Pacific.** *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 10(4), 72–79. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v10i4.4717>

Heryadi, D., Dewi, A. U., Akim, A., Hermawan, C., & Waki'ah, W. (2019). **Questioning the Regional Integration of Higher Education in ASEAN: Equality for All?** *JAS (Journal of ASEAN Studies)*, 6(2), 117–136. <https://doi.org/10.21512/jas.v6i2.5120>

Katigbak, A. V., Amante, E. (2019). **ASEAN integration into education in selected higher educational institutions: An analysis**. In *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts* (Vol. 3, No. 2C). Retrieved from <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/5376>

Pasciana, R., & Iriany, I. S. (2018). **ASEAN Integration In Improving Indonesian Women Education: A Literature Review**. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Politik Dan Humaniora*, 1(2), 42–45. <https://doi.org/10.36624/jisora.v1i2.15>

b. Online Journal Article

Birru, Y. T. (2024). **The Integration of 21st-Century Skills into the Higher Education Curriculum: Practices and Perspectives Systematic Review**. *Teacher Education and Curriculum Studies*, 9(3) 60-68. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.tecs.20240903.12>

Karatas, K. (2020). **The competencies of the culturally responsive teacher: What, why and how?** *inquiry in Education*, 12(2), Article 2. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1279513.pdf>

Milner, H. R. (2007). **Race, Culture, and Researcher Positionality: Working Through Dangers Seen, Unseen, and Unforeseen**. *Educational Researcher*, 36(7), 388-400. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X07309471>

c. Website

ASEAN. (2007, November 20). **Chairman's statement of the 13th ASEAN Summit:**

"One ASEAN at the heart of dynamic Asia" [Statement by Prime Minister Lee Hsien Loong, Chairman of the 13th ASEAN Summit]. Retrieved from [Chairman's Statement of the 13th ASEAN Summit, "One ASEAN at the Heart of Dynamic Asia" Singapore, 20 November 2007 - ASEAN Main Portal](#)

ASEAN. (2013, April 25). **Joint statement of the Ninth Brunei Darussalam–**

Indonesia–Malaysia–Philippines East ASEAN Growth Area Summit (9th BIMP-EAGA Summit), 25 April 2013, Bandar Seri Begawan, Brunei Darussalam. Retrieved from [Joint Statement of the Ninth Brunei Darussalam Indonesia Malaysia Philippines East ASEAN Growth Area Summit \(9th BIMP EAGA Summit\), 25 April 2013, Bandar Seri Begawan, Brunei Darussalam - ASEAN Main Portal](#)

Department of Education. (2024, August 26). **Philippines advocates for digital**

education reforms at ASEAN ministers meeting. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/philippines-advocates-for-digital-education-reforms-at-asean-ministers-meeting>

d. E-book with one author

Chang, H. (2008). **Autoethnography as Method.** Routledge.

<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315433370>

APPENDICES

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES
UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Maahas, Los Baños, Laguna 4031
(049) 536 6001 to 06 loc. 821, 333; 536-6010

APPROVAL SHEET

Master of ASEAN Studies

This Thesis Proposal entitled

**ENHANCING SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION THROUGH THE INTEGRATION OF ASEAN
PERSPECTIVES IN THE CURRICULUM: AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY OF A
TEACHER IN HIGHER EDUCATION**

submitted and presented by **Christian Jessie B. Bala**

in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree **Master of ASEAN Studies**

has been examined and is recommended for approval of
Proposal Presentation in ASEAN 300 on 05 December 2024.

Approved by the Student's Advisory Committee
with the following decision: APPROVED DISAPPROVED on 05 December 2024.
Additional remarks: _____

PROF. JEAN A. SALUDAQUEZ, PhD
Chair

PROF. PRIMO G. GARCIA, PhD
Member

DR. EMELY D. DICOLEN
Member

ASST. PROF. LORENA JEAN D. SALUDAQUEZ
Program Chair

PROPOSAL PRESENTATION REJOINDER

Name and Student Number: CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA
 Program: MASTER OF ASEAN STUDIES
 Title of Research: ENHANCING SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION THROUGH THE INTEGRATION OF ASEAN PERSPECTIVES IN THE CURRICULUM: AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY OF A TEACHER IN HIGHER EDUCATION
 Date Accomplished: MAY 07, 2025

¹Rejoinder:

Comments by Committee	Actions Taken	Page Number(s) of Actions Taken
Chapter 1		
The rationale of the study is too limited, making it difficult to comprehend fully.	The concept and practical application of the study's rationale have been clearly outlined.	1-2
The research questions lack focus and cover an overly wide range of topics.	The research questions have been refined to be more precise and focused.	2
Chapter 2		
Study does not include unpublished journals as references in the review of related literature.	Published journals that employ autoethnography as a research method have been utilized.	5-32
Chapter 3		
Avoid using multiple research questions to answer the research methods, as it can be time-consuming and complex.	Autoethnography has been employed as both a research method and methodology.	33-35

²RECOMMENDATION OF THE ADVISORY COMMITTEE:

	For Approval	For Disapproval
Chair: DR. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ		_____
Members: DR. EMELY D. DICOLEN DR. PRIMO G. GARCIA	 	_____ _____
 CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA Student	 DR. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ Committee Chair	

¹To be filled out by the Student
²To be filled out by the Committee

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES
UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Maahas, Los Baños, Laguna 4031
(049) 536 6001 to 06 loc. 821, 333; 536-6010

PROGRESS REPORT¹

Name and Student Number: CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA, 2021-32007
Program: Master of ASEAN Studies
Title of Research: INTEGRATING ASEAN PERSPECTIVE IN THE SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION: AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY OF A TEACHER IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Date Accomplished: July 14, 2025

1. Start of study: 07/04/2024	2. Expected end of study: 07/14/2025
3. Number of enrolled participants: Not applicable	4. Number of required participants: Not applicable
5. Number of participants who withdrew: Not applicable	
6. Deviations from the approved proposal: None	
7. New information (literature or in the conduct of the study) that may significantly change the study: None	
8. Issues/Problems encountered: None	
9. Others: None	

Adviser Feedback:

CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA
Student

DR. JEAN A. SALUDEZ
Committee Chair

¹To be filled out by the Student

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES
UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Maahas, Los Baños, Laguna 4031
(049) 536 6001 to 06 loc. 821, 333; 536-6010

MANUSCRIPT READINESS FOR FINAL DEFENSE PRESENTATION

Name and Student Number: Christian Jessie B. Bala, 2021-32007
Program: Master of ASEAN Studies
Title of Research: Integrating ASEAN perspective in the Social Studies Education: An autoethnographic study of a teacher in higher education
Date Accomplished: July 14, 2025

This is to certify that the manuscript is ready for committee members' feedback and approval for the sole purpose of student's application for the thesis defense presentation. This also certifies that the thesis committee members will be **present during the defense presentation**.

DR. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ
Chair

DR. PRIMO. G. GARCIA
Member

DR. EMELY D. DICOLEN
Member

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES
UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Maahas, Los Baños, Laguna 4031
(049) 536 6001 to 06 loc. 821, 333; 536-6010

NOTICE OF APPLICATION FOR THESIS DEFENSE

Name and Student Number: CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA, 2021-32007
Program: MASTER OF ASEAN STUDIES
Title of Research: **Integrating ASEAN perspective in the Social Studies Education: An autoethnographic study of a teacher in higher education**

Date Accomplished: July 14, 2025

This is to certify that the manuscript is ready for thesis defense.

RECOMMENDATION OF THE ADVISORY COMMITTEE:

	For Approval	For Disapproval
Chair: DR. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ	 _____	_____
Members: DR. PRIMO G. GARCIA	 _____	_____
DR. EMELY D. DICOLEN	 _____	_____

CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA
Student

DR. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ
Committee Chair

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES
UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Maahas, Los Baños, Laguna 4031
(049) 536 6001 to 06 loc. 821, 333; 536-6010

REPORT OF ORAL PRESENTATION AND DEFENSE

Name and Student Number: Christian Jessie B. Bala | 2012-22086
Program: Master of ASEAN Studies
Final Title of Research: **INTEGRATING ASEAN PERSPECTIVE IN THE SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION: AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY OF A TEACHER IN HIGHER EDUCATION**

Date, time, and place of the final defense: 18 July 2025, 1:00 PM, and via Zoom

Committee

Chair:
PROF. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ
Members:
PROF. PRIMO G. GARCIA

DR. EMELY D. DICOLEN

Signature

Digitally signed by Dicolen Emely Dulig
Date: 2025.09.11 11:04:11 +08'00'

Committee's Decision:

Approved Provisional Approval Subject to Provision Disapproved

Classification: Invention (I) Publication (P) Confidential (C) Free (F)

Additional remarks or recommendations:

With minor revisions on the formatting of the manuscript. Integrate the rationale mentioned by the panel members and FICs. Refine the phrasing of paragraph each chapter. Follow the MAS thesis manuscript format. Add relevant literature on the "ASEAN Integration in Higher Education" to strengthen chapter. Add the comments to strengthen the "Contribution to ASEANOLGY" based on the suggestion that emphasizing "ASEAN has to be appreciated in helping the student build ASEAN Identity", "Emphasize ASEAN not as a political and economic organization but a framework to build respect for diversity and cultural competence, and "the role of Filipino teachers to teach students the role of ASEAN in strengthening regional cooperation". Recommendations should be less and includes most important. Add to the recommendation the CMO No. 75, series of 2017.

Noted:

PROF. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ
Committee Chair

ASSOC. PROF. FINAFLOR F. TAYLAN
Dean

ASST. PROF. LORENA JEAN D. SALUDADEZ
Program Chair

THESIS DEFENSE REJOINER

Name and Student Number: BALA, CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. 2021-32007
 Program: Master of ASEAN Studies
 Title of Research: **INTEGRATING ASEAN PERSPECTIVE IN THE SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION: AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY OF A TEACHER IN HIGHER EDUCATION**

Date Accomplished: August 28, 2025

¹Rejoinder:

Comments by Committee	Actions Taken	Page Number(s) of Actions Taken
Chapter 1		
Refine the phrasing of paragraph	I refine the paragraph to make clearer rationale on the “ASEAN in higher education” and “ASEAN in teaching Social Studies Education”	1-3
Emphasize the ASEAN integration in “BSED Social Studies” in the rationale to make the rationale clear to the readers	I emphasize “ASEAN integrating in teaching BSED Social Studies” to distinguish it ASEAN in higher education	2
	I also add another paragraph to state the objectives, scope and delimitations and significance of the study in prose form.	2-3
Chapter 2		
Refine the phrasing of paragraph by emphasizing the ASEAN awareness in literature and the gaps	I refine the paragraph in the literature to emphasize the “lack of ASEAN awareness” and “lack of ASEAN centrality” to significant gaps, and how to address the gaps in the study	4-9
Add 2-3 literature for compliance, about ministerial meetings, summits, etc. to support the ASEAN centrality through ASEAN integration in higher education institutions	I added 3 literatures about ASEAN initiatives, ministerial meetings, summits, etc to emphasize ASEAN centrality. I added it to “ASEAN integration in higher education”	4-5
Chapter 3		
Refine the phrasing of paragraph	I refine the phrasing of paragraph to have a clearer discussion about the use of autoethnography and autoethnology as the research framework	10-11
Chapter 4		
Refine the phrasing of paragraph	I refine the phrasing on the data	13-16

¹To be filled out by the Student

²To be filled out by the Committee

THESIS DEFENSE REJOINDER

Comments by Committee	Actions Taken	Page Number(s) of Actions Taken
	gathering procedure, data sources, trustworthiness and credibility, and ethical considerations.	
Chapter 5		
Refine the phrasing of paragraph to practices and perspectives to make the discussion clear and not confusing	I refine the phrasing of paragraph to clarify the supporting literatures on “higher education teachers’ practices” and “higher education teacher’s perspectives”, and “relationship between teachers’ practices and perspectives”	26-28, 35-36, 46-48, 55, 73-77, 81-82, 84, 85-86, 87-88
Expand the discussion part	I expand the discussion part by discussing the objectives of Asian regionalism, inclusion of ASEAN as a central topic which includes seven subtopics, discussing the content of the clear guidelines, rubrics, and ratings in course assessments.	26-28, 35-36, 46-48, 55, 73-77, 81-82, 84, 85-86, 87-88
Chapter 6		
Refine the phrasing of paragraph to emphasize the utilization of collaborative learning strategies, emphasize teachers must prepare for cultural cooperation, emphasize the role of Filipino teachers to teach students regional cooperation	I refine the “Contribution of ASEANOLGY” based on the suggestion that emphasizing “ASEAN has to be appreciated in helping the student build ASEAN Identity”, “Emphasize ASEAN not as a political and economic organization but a framework to build respect for diversity and cultural competence, and “the role of Filipino teachers to teach students the role of ASEAN in strengthening regional cooperation”	91-92
Add CMO no. 75, 2017 to recommendations and recommendations should be less than in the presentation, include the most important ones	I include CMO No. 7 series of 2017 in the recommendation	92

¹To be filled out by the Student

²To be filled out by the Committee

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES
UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Maahas, Los Baños, Laguna 4031
(049) 536 6001 to 06 loc. 821, 333; 536-6010

THESIS DEFENSE REJOINDER

²General Comments/Remarks/Recommendations:

Note: *Actual comments and remarks may appear as comments in the actual defense.*

²RECOMMENDATION OF THE ADVISORY COMMITTEE:

- Defense is approved.
- Defense needs revision based on the general comments/feedback/recommendations.
 - For minor revision, to be submitted in 1-3 weeks.
 - For major revision, to be submitted in 4-6 weeks.
 - Resubmission up to a maximum of 3 months for the committee to reconvene.
- Defense is disapproved based on the general comments/feedback.

Noted:

DR. JEAN A. SALUADEZ
Committee Chair

ASST. PROF. LORENA JEAN D. SALUADEZ
Program Chair

DR. PRIMO G. GARCIA
Member

DR. EMELY D. DICOLEN
Member

¹To be filled out by the Student
²To be filled out by the Committee

UP OPEN UNIVERSITY
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
Research Ethics Committee

01 July 2025

MR. CHRISTIAN JESSIE B. BALA
Graduate Student, Master of ASEAN Studies
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
University of the Philippines Open University

RE: Enhancing Social Studies Education through the Integration of ASEAN Perspectives in the Curriculum: An Autoethnographic Study of a Teacher in Higher Education

FMDS REC No. 2025-006-GS-FMDS

Subject: Certificate of Exemption from Review

Dear **Mr. Bala**:

This is to acknowledge submission of the following documents dated 06 June 2025:

- 2025-Bala_ApprovalSheet.pdf
- 2025-Bala_DiagrammaticWorkflow.pdf
- 2025-Bala_EndorsementLetter.pdf
- 2025-Bala_Form 1(B)_CV.pdf
- 2025-Bala_Form 6(A)_ApplicationForm.pdf
- 2025-Bala_Form4(E2)_NonHealthRelateAssessmentForm.pdf
- 2025-Bala_Form6(D)_StudyProtocolAssessmentForm.pdf
- 2025-Bala_Form6(F)_ICFChecklist.pdf
- 2025-Bala_FullProtocol.pdf
- 2025-Bala_LetterRequest.pdf

After a preliminary review of the above documents, the Faculty of Management and Development Studies Research Ethics Committee deemed it appropriate that the above proposal be **EXEMPTED FROM REVIEW**.

This means that the study may be implemented without undergoing an expedited or full review. Neither will the proponents be required to submit further documents to the committee as long as there is no amendment nor alteration in the protocol that will change the nature of the study nor the level of risk involved.

Very truly yours,

REGINE KARLAP BAGALANON
External Vice Chair

FMDS Language Editing Certification Form

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES
UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Maahas, Los Baños, Laguna 4031
(049) 536 6001 to 06 loc. 821, 333; 536-6010

CERTIFICATION OF LANGUAGE EDITING

Name and Student Number: Christian Jessie B. Bala
Program: Master of ASEAN Studies
Title of Research: **INTEGRATING ASEAN PERSPECTIVE IN SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION: AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY OF A TEACHER IN HIGHER EDUCATION**

Date Accomplished: September 10, 2025

This is to certify that the manuscript has undergone professional editing (e.g. language, grammar, syntax).

CHERYLYN P. STA ANA, LPT, MLL
Editor

DR. JEAN A. SALUDADEZ
Committee Chair